

LEGITIMULT

Legitimate Crisis Governance in Multilevel Systems

Working Paper: Coding Criteria

WP1: Dataset and Quantitative Analysis

Authors: Arjan H. Schakel, Bilal Hassan

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Table of Contents

Executive summary	3
1. Introduction.	4
2. Why is there a need for a draft coding scheme on subnational authority?	5
3. When did the Covid-19 crisis begin and end?	6
4. What are Covid-19 governmental responses?	9
5. Which <u>subnational</u> Covid-19 governmental responses are included?	12
6. Why are socio-economic policies not included?	13
7. Which countries are included?	14
8. What are the (relevant) subnational governmental tiers?	16
9. Who are the (relevant) actors within subnational governmental tiers?	19
10. What are the possible policy responsibilities of subnational jurisdictions?	21
11. What are the possible shared policy responsibilities of subnational jurisdictions?	23
12. Draft coding scheme subnational authority in governmental policy.	27
13. Why are there different scores for subnational tiers and countries?	29
14. Why is the draft coding scheme applied to a corpus of legal documents?	30
15. Is the draft coding scheme feasible?	31
16. Are the indicators generalizable to other (types of) crises?	32
17. Which research questions can (not) be addressed with the draft coding scheme?	33
18. References	34
19. Appendix: Country profile The Netherlands (draft)	37

Executive summary

This working paper introduces a draft coding scheme to trace subnational authority in the governmental responses during the Covid-19 crisis. Existing measurements for decentralization such as the Regional Authority Index and the Local Autonomy Index do not trace any (de)centralization during the Covid-19 crisis because constitutions and laws on local and regional government were not changed and these indicators are not sufficiently fine-grained to tap changes in the allocation of policy provision competences between tiers of government. Yet, the involvement of subnational tiers in the governmental responses to the Covid-19 crisis varies widely between countries and over time. Furthermore, the Covid-19 crisis provides for a rare opportunity to test several hypotheses for the causes for and impacts of decentralized crisis responses. Hence, there is a strong need for an indicator that can trace subnational authority during crises.

In this working paper, we discuss the research rationale underlying the draft coding scheme, we detail conceptual choices and the development of indicators, we provide argumentation for the operationalization of the indicators, we address practical issues in relation to the application of the draft coding scheme, and we discuss the generalizability of the draft coding scheme to other crises.

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1. Introduction

Measures taken to mitigate and manage the Covid-19 pandemic by public authorities have highlighted substantial challenges of democratic governance. The governance of crises often requires speedy and coordinated actions which go beyond the normal decision-making and implementation processes and procedures in liberal democracies. Individual rights and freedoms and the vertical and horizontal separation of powers are endangered and comprised in a crisis. The Covid-19 crisis also put multilevel democratic governance under stress and national, centralized action interfered with local and regional government autonomy. However, the extent to which local and regional governments played a passive or active role varied highly between countries and within countries over time. In some federal and regionalized countries, regional governments played a role in the centralized responses from the start of the Covid-19 crisis through intergovernmental meetings between federal and regional (prime) ministers. In other countries, local and regional governments were put in charge to decide when businesses and schools should be closed or (re-)opened in response to local infection rates. This raises the research question of how subnational authority developed during the Covid-19 crisis?

Existing measures for decentralization cannot be used to trace subnational authority during the Covid-19 crisis. The Regional Authority Index (RAI; Hooghe et al. 2016; Shair-Rosenfield et al. 2021) taps formal authority exercised by regional governments and the coding is primarily based on legal documents such as constitutions, constitutional law, and laws on local and regional government, elections, finance, etc. Similarly, the Local Autonomy Index (LAI; Ladner et al. 2019, 2023) traces autonomy for local government and its coding is also based on legal documents. However, constitutions, constitutional laws, and laws on regional and local government were not modified, revised, annulled, or (temporarily) suspended. In addition, typical governmental responses during the Covid-19 crisis involved policies such as curfews, closing schools, workplaces and businesses, imposing hygiene measures in public spaces, facemask requirements in public transport, testing, contact tracing, and vaccination programs. Both the RAI and LAI include a policy scope sub-indicator, but these do not include these specific Covid-19 policies. Hence, tracing decentralization in the governmental responses during the Covid-19 crisis requires the development of a new indicator.

The Covid-19 crisis is a rare event that provides for a unique opportunity to test some key hypotheses in relation to decentralization during crisis governance. For example, a widely shared expectation in the literature is that crises lead to strong centralization of decision-making (Navarro and Velasco 2022). Federal and decentralized countries are thought to be less able to rapidly respond to crisis in a coordinated manner due to their greater susceptibility to political conflict (Hegele and Schnabel 2021; Kuhn and Morlino 2022). However, federalism and decentralization may also positively impact the effectiveness of crisis responses because it enables combining coordination with territorial differentiation according to local conditions (Steytler 2022). Yet, the extent to which federations responded to the Covid-19 crisis varies widely and raises new research questions in relation to decentralization during times of crisis (Rozell and Wilcox 2020). Addressing these research questions requires a sophisticated indicator that systematically traces subnational authority in the governmental responses during a crisis.

Studying decentralization during crises is also important because “decentralization outcomes—in terms of democracy, efficiency, accountability, regional and local government—depend greatly on the way decentralization is designed and implemented” (OECD 2019: 11). Decentralization has been hypothesized with outcomes that are relevant during crisis governance. Strong local and regional governments may check central government abuses and protect individual freedoms, subnational

governments are better able to elicit and make use of local information, and decentralization enhances accountability because voters have better information about local than about central government performance (Diamond 1999; Oates 1972; Treisman 2007). Furthermore, the involvement of subnational governments can be vital for the legitimacy of government policy especially during periods of crisis (Velasco-Guachalla et al. 2022; Vetter 2002).

In this paper we present a draft coding scheme that traces subnational authority in the governmental responses during the Covid-19 crisis. This working paper does not follow the standard format of an academic research paper with an introduction, a literature/theory section, data and methods, results, and discussion. The draft coding scheme we present is still work in progress and in this working paper we discuss the conceptual and empirical choices we have made, and we detail the arguments for why we have made these choices. To make our choices and argumentation explicit, we have structured the working paper in a question-and-answer format. The working paper will be discussed during the second LEGITIMULT-conference to be held in Ljubljana on April 18-19, 2024, to identify the next steps in the development of the draft coding scheme as well as its application.

We begin by discussing the need for a coding scheme on subnational authority (§2) and by outlining. We then discuss the temporal scope of the planned application of the draft coding scheme (§3) and the identification of Covid-19 governmental responses (§4), and we explain which sub-national governmental responses are included (§5) and why socio-economic policies are excluded (§6). After explaining the geographical scope of the planned application of the draft coding scheme (§7), we discuss for which subnational tiers (§8) and for which actors within the subnational tiers (§9; indicator ACTOR-SF) we will trace subnational authority. Our draft coding scheme assesses subnational authority along a self-rule dimension –i.e. authority exercised by a subnational jurisdiction over policy within its territory (§10; indicators DEPTH-SF; INDIRECT-SF)—as well as a shared rule dimension –i.e. authority collectively exercised by subnational and national governments over national policy (§11; indicators ACTOR-SH; DEPTH-SH). After a presentation of the full draft coding scheme (§12), we discuss how scores for subnational tiers are aggregated to the country level in case a country has two or more subnational tiers (§13). The final sections discuss the application and feasibility of the draft coding scheme (§14-§15) as well as the reliability and (external) validity of the draft coding scheme (§16-§17).

2. Why is there a need for a draft coding scheme on subnational authority?

The Covid-19 crisis has generated a research interest into the causes and consequences of a (de-)centralized crisis response (e.g. Greer et al. 2020; Toshkov, Carroll, and Yesilkagit 2022). The extent to which existing indicators for decentralization such as Regional Authority Index (RAI; Hooghe et al. 2016; Shair-Rosenfield et al. 2021) and the Local Autonomy Index (LAI; Ladner et al. 2019, 2023) can be used to validly tap subnational authority during the Covid-19 crisis can be questioned for two reasons.

First, a valid indicator must be policy specific. The Covid-19 governmental responses include a wide range of policies such as curfews, closing schools, workplaces and businesses, imposing hygiene measures in public spaces, facemask requirements in public transport, testing, contact tracing, and vaccination programs. Although both the RAI and LAI include a policy scope sub-indicator, these sub-indicators do not include the aforementioned Covid-19 policies. The RAI, and to a lesser extent the LAI, do not assess authority exercised within particular policies. The RAI codes three broad clusters of ‘economic policy’, ‘cultural-educational policy’ and ‘welfare policy’ and the LAI tracks local government responsibility in education, land use, police, social assistance, public transport, caring

functions, health, and housing. As a result, significant discrepancies can arise between RAI- and LAI-scores on the one hand, and actual subnational involvement in the Covid-19 crisis responses on the other hand. For example, regions in Denmark score 7 and Dutch provinces score 17.5 out of a maximum score of 30 on the RAI. Yet, in 2020, during the first year of the Covid-19 crisis, Danish regions were involved in the Covid-19 governmental response whereas Dutch provinces were hardly involved. Danish regions elect four out of a total of nine members of a regional epidemic committees which was responsible for implementing Covid-19 policies decided by the national government. Dutch provinces were not directly involved deciding or implementing Covid-19 responses until a national law was adopted by the national parliament in December 2020. Dutch provincial assemblies elect the representatives of the upper chamber of national parliament which has veto power over national legislation.

Second, a valid indicator must be sensitive to changes over time. The OECD (2021) reports that, since spring 2020, regional and local governments have been more actively adjusting their response measures to the local context. In addition, since December 2020, vaccination programs were rolled out which were mostly led by national governments, but their implementation was often done in coordination with subnational governments. Thus, there is empirical evidence that subnational authority in the Covid-19 responses may have changed over time. However, formal authority as measured by the RAI and LAI has not changed. Both the LAI and RAI tap formal authority exercised by subnational governments and the coding is primarily based on legal documents such as constitutions, constitutional law, and laws on local and regional government, elections, finance, etc. However, these legal documents were not modified, revised, annulled, or (temporarily) suspended.

In sum, tracing decentralization in the governmental responses during the Covid-19 crisis requires the development of a new indicator that is policy-specific and is sensitive to changes over time in the level of decentralization within those Covid-19 governmental responses.

3. *When did the Covid-19 crisis begin and end?*

The objective to measure subnational authority during the Covid-19 crisis entails that the research concerns a specific period. The literature offers many definitions of a crisis but most of these definitions include decision-making during a period of time when circumstances are uncertain and pressing, i.e. when a social system is experiencing a ‘threat’ (Rosenthal, ‘t Hart and Charles 1989; Rosenthal and Kouzmin 1997). “Crisis researchers typically focus on a temporal slice of the process through which a disaster emerges and eventually fades” (Boin, ‘t Hart, and Kuipers 2018: 23). Often, a crisis has a clear beginning and end, but an important characteristic of the Covid-19 pandemic is that it can be described as a ‘creeping crisis’ with unclear beginning and ends (Boin, Ekengren, and Rhinard 2020). It started with an increasing stream of worrying signals and the Covid-19 crisis eventually disappeared but returned in second and third waves (Boin, McConnel, and ‘t Hart 2021: 7). These observations raise the question when did the Covid-19 crisis begin and end?

The World Health Organization (WHO) declared the outbreak of the coronavirus disease caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) a ‘public health emergency of international concern’ on 30 January 2020. This declaration was ended on May 5, 2023.¹ Figure 3.1 displays the estimated daily excess deaths per 100,000 people (7-day rolling average) in Europe from March 1, 2020, to February 4, 2024. Figure 3.1 clearly reveals three major waves in excess deaths between January 2020 and June 2022 with clear peaks in April 2020, January 2021, and November

¹ <https://news.un.org/en/story/2023/05/1136367>

2021. Three minor waves in excess deaths have occurred between August and December 2022. There have not been any clear waves since January 2023.

The WHO declaration is based on the international spread of a disease (WHO 2005, Art. 1: 9) and Figure 3.1 reveals the excess death per 100,000 people in Europe. The governmental responses to the Covid-19 pandemic are not considered by the WHO or Figure 3.1. The Oxford Covid-19 Response Tracker (OxCGRT) provides three indicators for government Covid-19 responses: a stringency index (SI), a containment and health index (CHI), and an Economic Support Index (ESI). All indicators vary between 0 (no governmental activity) to 100 (maximum governmental activity) and scores are provided on a daily basis starting from January 1, 2020 and ending on 31 December 2022. Figure 3.2A presents average scores across 31 EU/EFTA countries and Figure 3.2B displays scores for each of the 31 EU/EFTA countries.

Estimated daily excess deaths per 100,000 people during COVID-19, Europe

For countries that have not reported all-cause mortality data for a given week, an estimate is shown, with uncertainty interval. If reported data is available, that value only is shown. On the map, only the central estimate is shown.

Figure 3.1

Data source: The Economist (2022); WHO COVID-19 Dashboard
 Note: For some countries, all-cause deaths and COVID-19 deaths use different date schemes, in which one refers to when the death occurred and the other to when it was reported. This difference could produce an artificial lag between the two time series.

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Source: Mathieu et al. (2020).

Figure 3.2A clearly reveals that the first Covid-19 governmental responses started in January 2020 and quickly peaked in March 2020. Governmental activity remained high throughout 2020 and 2021 and, after a third peak in January 2022, it started to decline to scores below 15 as of May 2023. Governmental activity varies widely between countries but the start and end of the Covid-19 crisis tend to overlap (Figure 3.2B). The first Covid-19 governmental responses begin in February-March 2020 and by the end of December 2022, 29 out of 31 EU/EFTA countries score below 12 and only Austria (score of 35) and Italy (score of 22) are exceptions (Mathieu et al. 2020).

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Figure 3.2A. Governmental Covid-19 responses in 31 European countries: averages.

Figure 3.2B. Governmental Covid-19 responses in 31 European countries.

Notes: Shown are (average) scores on the stringency index (SI), the containment and health index (CHI), and the Economic Support Index (ESI) from 1 January 2020 until 31 December 2022. Higher scores indicate more 'strictness', 'containment', and 'economic support'.

Source: Oxford Covid-19 Response Tracker (OxCGRT; Hale et al. 2021).

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4. What are Covid-19 governmental responses?

The Covid-19 crisis was first and foremost a public health crisis, but governmental responses that aimed to contain and avoid further spread of the virus impacted upon a wide range of policies. Schools, workplaces, hospitals, elderly and nursing homes were required to implement hygiene measures and schools and workplaces were closed for particular periods in time. Public events were cancelled, gatherings were restricted in terms of number of people that could attend, citizens were required to wear facemasks in the public sphere, and citizens were confronted with stay-at-home requirements. In addition, citizens were constrained regarding international and internal travel and the usage of public transport was subject to restrictions.

In addition to this wide range of *restrictive* policies, many Covid-19 governmental responses were *pro-active* in nature. Vaccination programs were quickly developed and rolled out, public health (e.g. facemasks) and hospital (e.g. respirators) equipment was collectively purchased, and testing and quarantine facilities were established. Later in the crisis, governments developed policy to provide income support for citizens and businesses who lost income caused by the Covid-19 restrictive governmental responses and governments took fiscal measures to finance these income support policies but also to cover the expenses of the Covid-19 crisis such as the increased intake of patients in hospitals and the rolling out of extensive vaccination programs.

The list of potential Covid-19 governmental responses is potentially long and diverse and there is no common understanding or agreement on what should or should not be considered a Covid-19 governmental response. We decided to take the Oxford Covid-19 Response Tracker (OxCGRT) as a starting point (Hale et al. 2021) for a list of Covid-19 policies for two reasons. First, the OxCGRT is the most extensive dataset both regarding the number of government responses as well as the time period covered. The OxCGRT tracks 25 policies on a daily basis beginning at 1 January 2020 until 31 December 2022. Other datasets either code a restricted number of policies or code a shorter period of time and does not include the whole Covid-19 crises period.² For example, the Response2covid19 dataset (Porcher 2020, 2023) focuses on public health responses and economic measures and does not include vaccination policies. In addition, the selection of certain public health responses appears incomplete and somewhat arbitrary. For example, one of the indicators is ‘closed restaurants’, and there are no other indicators for many other businesses that also have been subject to closing, such as bars, nightclubs, hotels, grocery stores, shopping centres, cinemas, barber shops, theme parks, retail, etc.

A major strength of the CoronaNet dataset is its level of detail. CoronaNet distinguishes between 20 broad policy types which are further subdivided into 177 sub-responses. The question arises whether such a level of detail is necessary given the research objective to code subnational authority regarding Covid-19 measures. For example, CoronaNet includes a ‘business restrictions index’ that tracks for 24 types of businesses whether they were subject to restrictions (Cheng et al. 2020). This may be a feasible approach for tracing when and how many policies were in place but, very often, rules were differentiated according to ‘essential’ and ‘non-essential’ businesses whereby the former were often exempted from the restrictions or were subject to less severe restrictions. In addition, the closing of non-essential and essential businesses was often regulated in one or few legislative documents which

² We focus on ‘policy trackers’ that offer the widest geographical, temporal, and policy coverage. The Oxford Supertracker The Global Directory for Covid Policy Trackers and Surveys (<https://supertracker.spi.ox.ac.uk>) lists a total of 232 entries. Most of the policy trackers focus on one or few countries, are limited in time (most often 2020 to early 2021), or include one or few policies.

also specifies the level of subnational authority in enforcing and implementing these restrictions. Ideally, an indicator provides the highest level of detail which, in this example, would require coding subnational authority regarding the closing of each (type of) business but there is a trade-off between the gain in measurement precision and the required resources to achieve this gain. We decided to take the OxCRGT policy scheme as the starting point for the draft coding scheme and we used the (sub-category) policy classification of CoronaNet to supplement and further specify the list of policies included in our draft coding scheme.

The Response2covid19 and CoronaNet datasets do not cover the whole timespan of the Covid-19 crisis. The former ends in June 2021, and the latter ends in May 2021 whereas the governments of the 31 EU/EFTA countries included in the LEGITIMULT-project were adopting responses throughout 2021. The restrictiveness indicator of the OxCRGT that varies between 0 (no restrictions) to 100 (maximum strictness) records among the 31 EU/EFTA countries in September 2021 scores that range between a low of 19 for Lithuania and a high of 58 for Greece. Thus, Covid-19 governmental responses were still prominent during the Fall of 2021 (see Figures 3.2A and 3.2B).

In addition to identifying Covid-19 governmental responses, adopting the policy classification of the OxCRGT has as a major benefit that subnational authority can be linked to the restrictiveness indicator of the OxCRGT. The Response2covid19 and CoronaNet datasets do not offer indicators that trace the level of strictness in the Covid-19 measures. Rather, they trace governmental (legislative) activism and record the scope –i.e. the ‘target population’—of the measures. By preserving a close link between the subnational authority indicator and the restrictiveness indicator of the OxCRGT, interesting research avenues are opened up. For example, considering that trust in local and regional government is (often) higher than trust in national government (Denters 2002; Jedwab and Kincaid 2018) one can hypothesize that the involvement of subnational authorities may have increased the perceived legitimacy of Covid-19 governmental policies, and that this impact is likely to be larger for measures that restrict the freedom of citizens.

The list of policies is neither definitive nor exhaustive, and we may add, delete, merge, or revise governmental responses. The list of policies is deductively derived from datasets that have traced Covid-19 governmental responses. The research objective behind the development of these datasets was to trace ‘government activity’ and the ‘strictness’ of governmental regulations. Our research objective is to trace subnational authority in the governmental responses/regulations and we also adopt an inductive approach whereby we will adjust the list of policies below according to the empirically observed Covid-19 governmental responses of subnational tiers. However, we will make sure that a (large) subset of policies remains compatible with the OxCRGT.

Covid-19 governmental responses

Containment and closure policies

School opening restrictions

1. Preschool or childcare facilities
2. Primary schools
3. Secondary schools
4. Higher education institutions

Business (workplace) opening restrictions

5. Public libraries, public museums/galleries, etc.
6. Hospitality businesses: Restaurants, bars, cinemas, hotels, sport facilities, etc.
7. Non-essential businesses: retail, shopping centres, etc.
8. Essential businesses: supermarket/grocery stores, pharmacies, etc.

Public event and outdoor spaces restrictions

9. Demonstrations
10. Festivals, concerts, sport events, etc.
11. Public outdoor spaces: parks, beaches, campsites, tourist sites, etc.

Gathering size restrictions

12. Curfew
13. Number and type of visitors in the home
14. Number and type of visitors outside the home
15. Funerals, weddings, church meetings, etc.

Public transport restrictions

16. Buses
17. Subways, trams
18. Trains

Quarantine requirements

19. Self-quarantine at home
20. Quarantine outside home (e.g. in a (assigned) hotel).

Internal movement restrictions

21. Health certificates; proofs of Covid-19 vaccination or Covid-19 test

International travel restrictions

22. Health screenings and/or certificates; travel history form; visa restrictions/extensions

Health system policies

23. Public information campaigns
24. Testing
25. Contact tracing
26. Vaccination
27. Regulations for educational institutions (e.g. from preschool to higher education, etc.)
28. Regulations for elderly care/nursing homes: visitors, hygiene, facial coverings, etc.
29. Regulations for hospitals: visitors, hygiene, facial coverings, etc.
30. Regulations for other health facilities: visitors, hygiene, facial coverings, etc.
31. Facial coverings: general requirements outside the home
32. Hygiene/distance measures: general requirements outside the home

5. Which subnational Covid-19 governmental responses are included?

Most Covid-19 governmental responses were decided by national governments but in relatively few instances subnational governments had the authority to decide their own Covid-19 governmental responses (i.e. when they score 4 on DEPTH-SF; see §10). In these instances, the subnational Covid-19 governmental responses may specify autonomy for other, lower-level subnational tiers. This can happen in federal and regionalized countries where regional authority includes control over local government: Austria, Belgium, Germany, Italy, Spain, Switzerland, and Northern Ireland, Scotland and Wales in the United Kingdom (Figure 7.1). In these seven countries, we code subnational Covid-19 governmental responses for authority exercised by lower-level subnational tiers. The number of regions that have control over local government is 100 (Table 8.1).³ Because of feasibility reasons, our initial focus will be on coding national governmental responses before we will code sub-national Covid-19 governmental responses for these seven countries. The coding of subnational Covid-19 governmental responses may have to wait until version 2.0 of the dataset.

The draft coding scheme sets out to measure formal subnational authority and we will not systematically code the actual practical use of authority by individual subnational jurisdictions. One important reason concerns feasibility. Subnational jurisdictions in a number of countries could decide to invoke restrictive measures in response to local circumstances. For example, Norway introduced a ‘traffic-light’ scheme whereby each ‘color’ stood for a particular set of rules regarding containment and closure and health system policies. Municipalities could decide to increase the restrictiveness of the measures by adjusting the ‘color’ for their jurisdiction. For example, if the national government decided that a ‘yellow’ regime applied in a particular region, then municipalities within that region could subsequently decide that a ‘red’ regime applied in their jurisdiction.⁴

Several Norwegian municipalities have decided to implement a stricter regime in their jurisdictions several times during the Covid-19 crisis. A systematic coding of the territorial differentiation entails tracing the restrictiveness of containment and closure and health system policies in 356 municipalities (Table 8.1) on a daily basis for a period of three years. Even a simplified coding tracing whether a municipality had a more (or less) restrictive regime requires collecting and (briefly) examining the decisions taken by 356 municipalities. Setting out to examine the territorial differentiation in containment and closure and health system policies is infeasible mainly because it changes the unit of analysis from a subnational tier to individual jurisdictions within a subnational tier (Table 8.1).

We decided to mention territorial differentiation in the country profiles when we encounter it –i.e. we find evidence for it. At a later stage, we may decide to operationalize territorial differentiation along two dummy variables that score positive for the days during which one or more different containment and closure or health system policies were applied in one or more individual jurisdictions. One dummy can trace territorial differentiation when subnational jurisdictions used their autonomy to apply a different Covid-19 governmental response. Another dummy can trace territorial differentiation due to a decision by the national government to apply a different Covid-19 governmental response in one or more subnational jurisdictions. It remains to be seen whether the detail mentioned in the country profiles is sufficient to validly and reliably code that Covid-19 governmental responses were territorially differentiated. It is important to note beforehand that the

³ 9 Austrian Länder, 5 Belgian regions/communities, 16 German Länder, 21 Italian regioni, 19 Spanish comunidades autonomas, 26 Swiss cantons, and 4 UK devolved territories.

⁴ Municipalities could not decide that a less restrictive regime applied in their jurisdictions. That is, they could not decide for a ‘green’ regime when the national government enforced a ‘yellow’ regime.

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collected information will not be sufficient to validly and reliably code the extent of territorial variation in containment and closure and health system policies (e.g. differences in the levels of restrictiveness) nor to determine which specific subnational jurisdiction during which specific periods in time differentiated in their Covid-19 governmental responses (e.g. in which exact municipalities a particular 'Covid-19 regime' was (not) applied).

6. *Why are socio-economic policies not included?*

Socio-economic policies are an important part of the governmental responses to the Covid-19 crisis. However, there are three reasons for why we do not measure subnational autonomy in socio-economic governmental responses. First, a literature review reveals that, apart from regionalized and federal countries (Figure 7.1), involvement of subnational tiers is minimal, especially when compared to the containment and health policies (e.g. Guderjan et al. 2023; Maher, Hoang, and Hindery 2020; Warner et al. 2021). Fiscal compensatory measures to dampen the effects of income loss because of the closure of businesses and citizens losing their jobs often exceed the budgetary capacities of subnational governments. Hence, national governments develop and finance the socio-economic responses to the Covid-19 crisis. Very often, national tax authorities administer these programs using online tools that do not require the involvement of subnational governments. Furthermore, the nascent literature seems to suggest that subnational tiers, and especially local governments, were recipients of economic support packages (e.g. Kössler 2022). Ideally, we would have preferred to include socio-economic policies, but for practical resource purposes we decided that socio-economic governmental responses have less priority than containment and health policies. In addition, WP4 in the LEGITIMULT-project specifically focuses on multilevel governance in the socio-economic governmental responses.

A second reason not to include socio-economic responses in our indicator is because the available evidence suggests that the developments in socio-economic governmental responses over time and across countries is quite different from the developments observed for containment and closure and health system policies. Figure 3.2A clearly reveals three 'waves' in governmental responses (i.e. 'governmental activism' or 'strictness of policies') concerning containment and closure (SI-indicator) and health system (CHI-indicator) policies (see §3). The 'peak' of the third wave occurred in January 2022 after which most containment and closure and health system policies were gradually wended down. In stark contrast, the governmental responses regarding socio-economic policies (ESI-indicator) does not reveal a 'wave-structure'. Rather a peak is observed around four months (April 2020) and governmental activism slowly declines from 80% in April 2020 to 63% in January 2022. In the third year of the crisis (2022), the rate of decline is comparable across the three indicators although ESI-scores are higher most of the time.

A closer look in the 31 individual countries reveal quite different developments over time for the ESI indicator whereas the three waves over time in the SI- and CHI-indicators are 'replicated' in each of the 31 European countries, although the timing and the height and width of the waves differ. In December 2022, ESI-index scores 100% in Austria, Cyprus, Germany, Greece and Lithuania whereas scores are 0% in Belgium, Denmark, France, Poland, and Slovenia (and in some other countries). Hence, the socio-economic governmental Covid-19 responses are in full swing in some countries but are terminated in other countries. Furthermore, the developments over time in ESI-scores are quite different across the countries: one long wave in Norway, Ireland, Slovakia and Sweden and two or more waves in Belgium, Czech Republic, Croatia, Hungary, and Iceland. The upshot is that the 'crisis-

experience' regarding socio-economic governmental responses is less comparable across European countries than for containment and closure and health system policies.

Comparability in 'governmental activism' over time is desirable to identify the causes for and impacts of subnational authority in governmental responses. It is methodologically more challenging to differentiate causes for and the impact of 'government activism' from the causes for and impacts of 'subnational authority' when developments in governmental activism over time is quite different across countries. The 'three waves' in the containment and closure and health system governmental responses can be exploited to isolate the causes for and impacts of subnational authority in the Covid-19 governmental responses because the involvement of subnational tiers did significantly change during the Covid-19 crisis in many countries. In addition to above mentioned high level of national government involvement in the design and implementation of socio-economic Covid-19 responses, the absence of 'waves' in ESI-scores in many of the countries limits the possibility to systematically compare the causes for and impacts of the involvement of subnational tiers.

A third reason not to include socio-economic responses in our indicator concerns the validity and reliability of the ESI-indicator. In stark contrast to the SI- and CHI-indicators, the ESI-indicator is based on only two sub-indicators whereas the SI- and CHI-indicators are based on respectively 9 and 14 sub-indicators (Hale et al. 2023: 101). In general, the reliability of an indicator increases to the extent that it is constructed from more sub-indicators. The two economic sub-indicators of the OxCRGT concerns income support –providing direct cash payments to unemployed people or who cannot work—and debt/contract relief –freezing financial obligations—for households (Hale et al. 2023: 53). Income support and debt relief for business and corporations is not included (Hale et al. 2023: 89) whereas this is an important part of the socio-economic governmental responses.

7. Which countries are included?

The geographical coverage is given by the parameters set by the LEGITIMULT project and 31 countries are included in the coding exercise (Figure 7.1). These are the 27 EU member states, three EFTA countries (Iceland, Norway, and Switzerland), and the United Kingdom.⁵ This case selection is sufficient to explore the involvement of subnational governments in the decision-making and implementation of Covid-19 governmental responses. First, this case selection includes the relevant empirical variation in the main independent variable, i.e. authority for local and regional governments. Using the LAI and the RAI, one can distinguish between four broad categories based on either low or high scores on either one of the indicators (Figure 7.1)⁶:

⁵ The 27 member states of the EU are: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, and Sweden.

⁶ As can be gauged from Figure 7.1, these are not mutually exclusive categories regarding total subnational authority. For example, total subnational authority in Iceland (40%) which has only a local tier may exceed total subnational authority (39%) in Poland which has a relatively strong regional (15%) and a stronger local (24%) government. Weak local governments can be found in regionalized and federal countries as well as in the countries that have relatively strong regional governments. The categorization does not take into account significant variation across regions within a country. For example, Northern Ireland, Scotland and Wales exercise significant regional authority in the United Kingdom.

- Centralized countries with weak local and no or very weak regional authority (e.g. Cyprus, Hungary, Latvia, Slovenia,).
- Centralized countries with strong local autonomy and relatively weak or no regional authority (e.g. Finland, Slovakia, Iceland, Estonia).
- Centralized countries with local and regional governments that both exercise significant autonomy (e.g. the Netherlands, Czech Republic, Romania, Sweden).
- Regionalized and federal countries where both local and regional governments have relatively strong autonomy and where shared rule –i.e. regular meetings between regional and national governments—takes place (e.g. Belgium, Germany, Italy, Switzerland).

Figure 7.1. Authority for local and regional governments in 47 countries.

Notes: Thirty-eight European countries and an additional nine OECD-countries clustered by their regional authority index (RAI) and local autonomy index (LAI) scores in 2018. RAI and LAI country scores are rescaled to 0% (minimum score) to 100% (maximum score), summed and divided by two. A country can score 100% when both its LAI- and RAI-scores are the maximum scores among the 47 countries. Sources: Hooghe et al. (2016); Ladner et al. (2019); Ladner, Keuffer, and Bastianen (2023); Shair-Rosenfield et al. (2021).

In addition, the sample of 31 countries are included in both the LAI and RAI. This has two main advantages. First, the LAI and RAI include detailed country profiles that discuss in detail the authority of local and regional governments. In case of the LAI, this detail also includes responsibilities of local government in the provision of 16 policies. Second, the RAI identifies and scores all intermediate tiers in between the local and national levels and that meet the average population criterion of 150,000 inhabitants. These advantages enable and significantly enhance the development of a draft coding scheme that is policy specific (see §4) and that separately codes subnational tiers (see §8) and specific actors within those subnational tiers (see §9).

8. What are the (relevant) subnational governmental tiers?

The aim of WP1 is to code subnational authority in the Covid-19 governmental responses. A necessary first step is to define which subnational tiers exercise governmental authority. A second step is to determine which subnational tiers should be taken into consideration while assessing the role of subnational governments in the Covid-19 governmental responses. Following the conceptual frameworks of the Regional Authority Index (RAI) and the Local Autonomy Index (LAI), we focus on general-purpose administration that have legislative and/or executive institutions. Table 8.1 lists 68 subnational tiers for 31 European countries that exercised government authority before the onset of the Covid-19 crisis, i.e. in January 2020. These 68 subnational tiers are responsible for a range of policies which they often combine with representative institutions such as assemblies, councils, and parliaments as well as various kinds of executives such as boards, governments, mayors, presidents, prefects, etc. Most of these 68 subnational tiers are responsible for one or more policy areas that were affected by the Covid-19 government responses such as education, public health, or transport. In addition, these were the subnational tiers at the disposal of central (and regional) governments to roll out various Covid-19 governmental responses such as vaccination programs, public information campaigns, and track-and-trace administration.

Task-specific subnational governments are not included in Table 8.1 because, with very few exceptions, they lack representative institutions, and they are often under direct control of a national (or regional) ministry.⁷ Hence, subnational authority is very limited in these instances.⁸ Table 8.1 lists seven deconcentrated central or regional state administration which are indicated with one asterisk. These tiers do not have institutions with indirectly or directly elected representatives apart from *oblasti* in Bulgaria and *kumitat reġjonali* in Malta which assemblies consisting of the mayors from the municipalities (*obshtini/kunsil lokali*) within their jurisdictions.⁹ All seven tiers have a one-headed executive who is appointed by the central or regional government and who is responsible for the implementation of a wide range of central or regional government policies, including policy areas impacted by Covid-19 governmental responses.

We decided not to include ‘planning regions’ which are deconcentrated central government administrations whose main responsibility is to manage EU Cohesion Funds.¹⁰ These subnational tiers are classified by the RAI as general purpose because the implementation of EU Cohesion Fund policy may include several policy areas such as economic development, (vocational) education, environmental protection, and public transport. However, their authority beyond economic development is limited and often concerns only aspects of a policy that may be impacted by an economic development program rather than significant authority over the policy itself. For example, building a train station, building a highway, or the development of a nature reserve. Considering their

⁷ One example of task specific government that have representative institutions are Dutch waterboards (*watershappen*) which main tasks are to regulate the water (ground) levels, to secure water quality, and to maintain dikes, rivers, and waterflows. The councils of Dutch waterboards (*algemeen bestuur*) are directly elected except for four seats out of a total of 18 to 30 seats. Another example are the Finnish health regions (*aluevaalit*) which have directly elected assemblies since January 1, 2023.

⁸ Many cantons are divided into *Bezirke* or *Amter* and these are not included because these function as electoral constituencies or as court districts, or they have very limited administrative purposes (Mueller 2015).

⁹ In addition, *Regierungsbezirke* in *Nordrhein-Westfalia* (Germany) have assemblies composed of local elected representatives of *Kreisfreie Städte* and *Landkreise*.

¹⁰ The following eight subnational tiers (‘planning regions’) are excluded: *Regiony soudržnosti* (Czech Republic), *Tervezési-statisztikai régiók* (Hungary), Regional assemblies (Ireland), *Plānošanas reģioni* (Latvia), *Regionų plėtros tarybos* (Lithuania), *Comissões de cooperação e desenvolvimento regional* (Portugal), *Regiuni de dezvoltare* (Romania), and *Regionalne razvojne agencije* (Slovenia).

limited and specific policy portfolio, ‘planning regions’ are not likely to have been involved in the Covid-19 crisis. However, it is important to note that ‘planning regions’ may have had a role in the *economic* Covid-19 governmental responses (see §6 for why socio-economic responses are excluded).

The exclusion of specific-purpose governments does not mean that the role of task-specific governmental bodies during the Covid-19 crisis is ignored. Rather, the level of involvement of specific actors from the subnational tiers listed in Table 8.1 in those task-specific governments needs to be exposed. For example, Dutch safety regions (*veiligheidsregios*) are responsible for fire protection, disaster and crisis management (including medical assistance), and public order and safety for crises that transcend municipal boundaries. The 25 safety regions played a major role in the Covid-19 governmental responses and indirectly involved Dutch municipalities because the mayors (chair of the executive) of the municipalities within a safety region form the council and executive of a safety region.¹¹

Another example are the five Danish epidemic committees (*epidemikommisionerne*) which are established by national law and were in place before the Covid-19 crisis hit and which were dealing with the crisis until all authority in relation to taking restricting measures was transferred to the Minister of Health in early March 2020. A regional epidemic committee consists of nine members: four members appointed by the regional council –one representative from the regional hospital emergency agency (*regionale sygehusberedskab*) and three members of the regional council (*regionsråd*)—and one representative appointed by, respectively, the chief of the national policy, the board of the patient safety agency, the veterinary and food administration, the customs and tax administration, and by the emergency management agency. Hence, the regional councils were indirectly involved in the Covid-19 governmental responses during the first month of the crisis, but they constituted a minority in the committee and had to share their authority with representatives appointed by national agencies.

Table 8.1 includes subnational tiers that cover the whole statewide territory and special autonomous regions that cover a (very) small part of a country’s territory or population are excluded.¹² This does not mean that each part of the statewide territory is governed by the same number of subnational levels. For example, seven *comunidades autónomas* in Spain are ‘uniprovincial’ and they combine provincial and autonomous community competences, but they have only one assembly and one executive. Citizens in these seven regions are governed by two and not three subnational tiers. In other instances, a subnational tier in Table 8.1 includes several different types of jurisdictions whose authority (policy scope) may differ. For example, each of the almost 35,000 municipalities in France are member of either a *métropole*, *communauté urbaine*, *communauté d’agglomération*, or *communauté de communes* which each have a different set of competences imposed by national law. In yet another group of instances, a local government law allocates a different set of competences to municipalities depending on their population sizes. For example, Spanish municipalities with a population size over 5,000 inhabitants have their own local police, social services and sporting facilities are included in the policy portfolios of municipalities with over 20,000 inhabitants, and public transport is the responsibility of municipalities with more than 50,000 inhabitants. The country profiles will specify the specific subnational tier that is involved in a Covid-19 governmental response. The dataset will include an indicator that states the percentage of the statewide population that is governed by the specific subnational tier.

¹¹ Further detail is provided in the draft country profile on the Netherlands in the appendix.

¹² The following seven special autonomous regions are excluded: Faroe Islands and Greenland in Denmark, Åland in Finland, Mount Athos in Greece, Svalbard in Norway, and the Açores and Madeira in Portugal.

Table 8.1. Subnational government tiers in 31 European countries.

Countries with one subnational tier (N = 6)					
Country	N	Tier name(s)	Country	N	Tier name(s)
Estonia	79	Vald/Linn	Lithuania	60	Savivaldybė
Iceland	69	Sveitarfélög	Luxembourg	102	Commune
Latvia	42	Novads/Valstspilsēta	Slovenia	212	Občina
Countries with two subnational tiers (N = 15)					
Country	N	Tier name(s)	Country	N	Tier name(s)
Bulgaria	28	Oblasti*	Netherlands	12	Provincies**
	265	Obshtina		352	Gemeenten
Croatia	21	Županije	Norway	11	Fylkeskommune**
	556	Općine/Grad		356	Kommune
Cyprus	6	Eparchie*	Portugal	23	Comunidades intermunicipais/ Área Metropolitana
	527	Koinotites/Dimoi		3400	Freguesias/Municípios
Czech Republic	14	Kraje	Romania	41	Judete**
	6248	Obec		3181	Comune/Orase/Municipii
Denmark	5	Regioner	Slovakia	8	Samosprávny kraje
	98	Kommuner		2930	Obec/Mesto/Mestská část
Hungary	42	Megyék/Megyei jogú városok	Sweden	21	Regioner**
	3154	Települések		290	Kommuner
Ireland	31	City/County councils	Switzerland	26	Cantons
	95	Municipal districts		2131	Gemeinden
Malta	5	Kumitat Regionali*			
	68	Kunsil lokali			
Countries with three subnational tiers (N = 8)					
Country	N	Tier name(s)	Country	N	Tier name(s)
Austria	9	Länder	Italy	21	Regione
	94	Bezirke*/Statutarstädte		107	Province**/Città metropolitane
	2095	Gemeinden		7904	Comuni
Belgium	5	Gewesten/Gemeenschappen	Poland	16	Województwo**
	10	Provincies**		380	Powiaty/Miasto na prawach powiatu
	581	Gemeenten		2477	Gminy
Finland	6	Aluehallintovirastot*	Spain	19	Comunidades/Ciudades autónomas
	20	Maakunnanliitto		52	Provincias/Cabildo insulares/ Consejos insulares
	309	Kunta		8131	Municipios
Greece	7	Apokentroménés dioikíseis*	United Kingdom	4	Devolved authorities
	13	Peripheria		10	Combined authorities
	332	Dimos		398	Local authorities
Countries with four subnational tiers (N = 2)					
Country	N	Tier name(s)	Country	N	Tier name(s)
France	13	Régions**	Germany	16	Länder
	96	Départements**		19	Regierungsbezirke*
	1253	Métropoles/Communautés urbaines/d'agglomération/ de communes**		401	Landkreise/Kreisfreie Städte
	34965	Communes		10799	Gemeinden

Notes: * Deconcentrated central/regional government administration; ** Dual executives.

Sources: CEMR (2021); Hooghe et al. (2016); Ladner et al. (2019); Ladner, Keuffer, and Bastianen (2023); Shair-Rosenfield et al. (2021).

The authority exercised by subnational governments during the Covid-19 crisis will be examined by tracing the involvement of the 68 subnational tiers displayed in Table 8.1 in the list of Covid-19 governmental responses scheme listed in s §4. Our draft coding scheme enables a tier-specific focus as well as a country-level focus. For example, one may hypothesize that the involvement of a particular tier depends on its regional (RAI-score) or local (LAI-score) autonomy before the crisis began. The impact of subnational authority in the Covid-19 governmental responses can be assessed by summing up the involvement of one or all subnational tiers within a country. By evaluating all subnational tiers simultaneously, one may better appreciate the total degree of centralization the Covid-19 governmental responses entailed. In addition, our draft coding scheme enables the evaluation of policy-subnational tier dyads. For example, kindergartens and primary schools are often the competence of municipalities, regional tiers often are responsible for secondary schools, whereas the policy portfolio of regions in the more populous countries often includes higher education. It is likely that the involvement of these tiers as well as the degree of ‘experienced (de)centralization’ will differ across subnational tiers depend on their specific policy portfolios. In other words, our draft coding scheme that differentiates between several Covid-19 responses and various subnational tiers enables one to address several research questions in relation to the causes and impacts of subnational authority in the Covid-19 governmental responses.

9. Who are the (relevant) actors within subnational governmental tiers?

A subnational tier is not a unitary actor, and several types of actors can be involved in the Covid-19 governmental responses. First, with few exceptions, all subnational tiers listed in Table 8.1 consist of a legislature –assembly, council—and an executive. It is important to differentiate between ‘legislative’ and ‘executive’ actors because one of the main hypotheses and empirical findings is that the urgency and immediacy of crises often lead to executive dominance (Lozano, Atkinson, and Mou 2023; Posner and Vermeule 2009; Szöcsik 2023). Differentiating between legislative and executive actors at the subnational level enables an assessment of the hypothesis whether an increase in executive dominance during the Covid-19 crisis also occurred at the subnational level.

The literature points out that parliaments can make crucial contribution to the political legitimacy of Covid-19 emergency governance (Griglio 2020; Petrov 2020; Szöcsik 2023). A particularity at the subnational level is that legislative bodies such as parliaments, councils, and assemblies can be directly elected by citizens, or they are indirectly elected by representatives from local assemblies or consist of municipal mayors. Similar to the parliamentary-executive relations at the national level, subnational executives can be directly elected by citizens or indirectly (s)elected by the legislative branch. However, at the subnational level there are also ‘dual administrations’ whereby executive authority is shared between executives appointed by the national government or by a higher subnational tier and an (in)directly elected executive (s)elected from within the subnational jurisdiction.

Entries with two asterisks (**) in Table 8.1 indicates the presence of a dual administration. There are two different types of dual administrations. In Belgium and the Netherlands, the chair of the provincial executive is appointed by the central government whereas the other members of the executive are appointed by the members of the provincial assembly. In France, Poland, Italy, Norway, Romania, and Sweden there are subnational tiers where subnational legislative and executive actors co-exist with an executive actor who is appointed by the central government and who heads a separate administration. These ‘prefects’ and their administrations are often responsible for implementing central government law and regularly exercise ex ante or ex post legal oversight of decisions from legislative and executive actors from jurisdictions across the subnational tier.

Deconcentrated central state administrations –indicated with one asterisk (*) in Table 8.1 —have appointed executives which often consist of only one member. The executives of *Bezirke* in Austria and *Regierungsbezirke* in Germany are appointed by *Land* governments, and the executives of *eparchies* in Cyprus, *aluehallintovirastot* in Finland, *apokentroménes dioikíseis* in Greece, and *kumitat regionali* in Malta are appointed by the central government. *Oblasti* in Bulgaria have assemblies that consist of mayors and assembly representatives from municipalities within the subnational jurisdiction and the assemblies of *Regierungsbezirke* in North-Rhine Westphalia in Germany are composed of representatives from *Kreisfreie Städte* and *Landkreise*.

Differentiating between different types of legislative and executive actors –i.e. whether they are indirectly or directly elected and whether they are appointed by central or regional governments—is important to be able to assess the democratic legitimacy of subnational involvement in the Covid-19 governmental responses. Especially in the case of dual administrations the involvement of a subnational tier may need to be qualified when competences are assigned to an actor at the subnational level that is acting based on instructions provided by the central and regional government rather than exercising authority on behalf of (in)directly elected subnational representatives.

The indicator ACTOR-SF traces the type of legislative or executive actor who is involved in the governmental response (Table 9.1). This is a nominal variable with six different actor-types that can be found within a subnational tier. Scoring the involvement of an actor always involves an executive because all the subnational tiers listed in Table 8.1 have an executive. When an assembly exercises authority then the involvement of an executive is implied because the executive implements the decisions taken by the assembly. A government response can be decided by an executive who is obliged to ask for advice or input from an assembly or other members of the executive before taking a decision. In these instances, the depth of the authoritative competences of a subnational actor determines which actor’s involvement will be scored. In other words, the involvement of the actor with the highest DEPTH-SF score –see §10—will be scored for a particular policy.

Table 9.1. Indicator ACTOR-SF.

ACTOR-SF: <i>The actor from a subnational tier who exercises the competences for a policy.</i>	
0 =	No subnational actor is involved.
1 =	An executive appointed by the central government.
2 =	An executive appointed by the regional government.
3 =	An indirectly elected executive appointed by the assembly.
4 =	An executive directly elected by citizens.
5 =	An indirectly elected assembly with representatives (s)elected from jurisdictions within the subnational tier.
6 =	An assembly directly elected by citizens.

10. What are the possible policy responsibilities of subnational jurisdictions?

Covid-19 legislation is unique for each country and the extent of involvement is unique for each subnational tier as well as for actors within the subnational tiers. The challenge of coding the responsibilities of subnational tiers in the Covid-19 responsibilities is to develop an indicator that validly and reliably taps subnational involvement in a policy. A valid indicator means that it covers the empirically observed variation as well as meaningfully distinguishes lower levels from higher levels of involvement. A reliable indicator requires that the indicator has clear criteria or thresholds that are clearly identifiable in the empirical material and that enhance consistency in scores across multiple coders.

Based on preliminary research on Covid-19 governmental responses in ten countries, we developed a DEPTH-SF indicator that measures the extent to which a subnational tier is responsible for a policy (Table 10.1).¹³ DEPTH-SF can obtain five scores that vary between no or very weak competences (= 0) to authoritative (decision-making) competences (= 4). Intermediate scores indicate that a subnational tier implements national rules but has some additional authoritative competences. A subnational tier may decide whether criteria specified in rules specified by higher tiers do (not) apply (= 1), a subnational tier can decide that additional rules apply than those specified by a higher tier (= 2), or a subnational tier can in addition to specifying supplementary rules also decide that higher tier rules do not apply in the subnational jurisdiction (= 3). In most instances, the higher tier is the national government but when a subnational tier has authority over the rules (i.e. it scores 4 on DEPTH-SF), then lower-level subnational tiers may be granted responsibilities in the implementation of regional rules.

An example of a case that meets the lower threshold for a score of 1 concerns the competences granted to the Dutch mayors with the adoption of a temporary Covid-19 law. Mayors could grant three types of exemptions in relation to national rules on maximum group size gatherings, closing or (partly) opening of public spaces, and events. The exercise of this competence was circumscribed, and mayors had to consult the municipal health service before taking a decision and they had to consider the type of location, type of activity, and the number of persons in their decisions. The explanatory memorandum to the temporary Covid-19 law also mentioned that mayors should apply their competences with restraint.¹⁴

Table 10.1. Indicator DEPTH-SF.

DEPTH-SF: <i>The extent to which a subnational tier is responsible for a policy.</i>	
0 =	No or very weak authoritative competencies.
1 =	Responsible for the implementation of higher tier rules and the competence to decide whether criteria specified in higher tier rules do (not) apply.
2 =	Responsible for the implementation of higher tier rules and the competence to decide on additional rules.
3 =	Responsible for the implementation of higher tier rules and the competence to decide on additional rules and to amend higher tier rules including deciding to (not) enforce national rules.
4 =	Authoritative (decision-making) competences for rules.

¹³ Very first drafts of country profiles can be found in the LEGITIMULT Microsoft Team folder of WP 1.

¹⁴ Further detail is provided in the draft country profile on the Netherlands in the appendix.

An exemplary case of a score of 2 concerns Norwegian municipalities that could decide to enforce stricter rules in their jurisdictions than those decided by the national government. A national law defined four levels of restrictiveness in the Covid-19 measures from the most lenient level A to the most restrictive level D. Municipalities were obliged to implement the measures of the level decided by the national government, but municipalities were free to decide to enforce a stricter level.

An example of a score of 3 is provided by Italy. Italian *regioni* could, for a short period in 2020, increase or decrease the stringency of Covid-19 measures. *Regioni* had to inform the ministry of health and national legislation should not yet be enforced.

German *Länder* exemplify a score of 4. In Germany, the Covid-19 governmental responses were, with few exceptions, the full competence of German *Länder* during 2020. The federal government assumed a coordinating role and provided recommendations to the *Länder*. Importantly, the *Länder* met with the federal government to coordinate (and co-decide) their Covid-19 governmental responses, but this is captured by the shared rule indicators (see §11).

Our preliminary research has revealed instances where subnational tiers were indirectly involved in the Covid-19 governmental responses.¹⁵ This means that a subnational tier is not directly involved nor is granted competences but another governmental body that includes actors from a subnational tier is involved and/or has been granted competences. Above we mentioned the example of five Danish epidemic committees whereby four out of a total of nine members are appointed by the regional council whereas the other five members were appointed by national (expert) agencies. The involvement of the regional council was indirect because regional representatives constituted a minority in the epidemic committee. Another example are the earlier mentioned 25 Dutch safety regions whose members were the mayors of the municipalities from within the jurisdiction of a safety region. In this instance, the involvement of a subnational tier is direct because competences are not shared with other actors apart from mayors from other municipalities. However, authority bestowed to the safety region is shared, i.e. the safety region is an intergovernmental body that exercises horizontal shared rule among municipalities.

To accommodate for indirectly exercised authority by subnational tiers we develop the indicator INDIRECT-SF that scores 0 when authority is exercised directly, 0.5 when authority is shared with other actors and the subnational tier cannot veto or override decisions, and 1 when authority is shared with actors from jurisdictions within the same subnational tier (Table 10.2).¹⁶ The authority exercised by a subnational tier can be adjusted for indirect rule by multiplying DEPTH-SF with INDIRECT-SF. The rationale for keeping DEPTH-SF scores unaltered by multiplying it with a score of 1 on INDIRECT-SF is because authority exercised by a subnational *tier* is similar when the authority is assigned to each jurisdiction/unit separately within a tier or when it shared by groups of jurisdictions/units. For example, all the mayors from the 342 Dutch municipalities were involved in the Covid-19 governmental responses but their authority was exercised through 25 safety regions instead of in the 342 municipalities. The observations that score 1 on the indicator enables researchers to identify instances of horizontal shared rule and to adjust DEPTH-SF or ACTOR-SF scores as they see fit for research purposes.

¹⁵ Very first drafts of country profiles can be found in the LEGITIMULT Microsoft Team folder of WP 1.

¹⁶ We prefer to adopt the label 'indirect rule' instead of shared rule to avoid confusion with the shared rule indicators ACTOR-SH and DEPTH-SH discussed in §11.

The Danish example of epidemic committees result in the following scores: An epidemic committee implements a national regulatory framework laid down in a national (infectious diseases) law (*Epidemiloven*) whereby the epidemic committee can decide to adopt stricter regulations than those specified in the national law (DEPTH-SF = 2). Regional councils (ACTOR-SF = 6) appoint four out of a total of nine members of the epidemic committee and these four representatives cannot veto or override the decisions taken by the epidemic committee (INDIRECT-SF = 0.5). The Dutch example of safety regions results in the following scores: A safety region implements a national regulatory framework laid down in a national law whereby the safety region can decide to adopt stricter regulations than those specified in the national law (DEPTH-SF = 2). Safety regions consists of the mayors of the municipalities (ACTOR-SF = 3) from within the safety region (INDIRECT-SF = 1). The multiplication of the scores on the DEPTH-SF and INDIRECT-SF indicators results in a higher overall score for Dutch safety regions ($2 \times 1 = 2$) than for Danish epidemic committees ($2 \times 0.5 = 1$) suggesting that subnational involvement was larger in the Netherlands than in Denmark.

Table 10.2. Indicator INDIRECT-SF.

INDIRECT-SF: <i>The extent to which a subnational tier shares responsibility for a policy.</i>	
0 =	The subnational tier does not share responsibility for a policy.
0.5 =	The subnational tier shares responsibility for a policy with other non-governmental actors and it cannot veto decisions taken by the intergovernmental body.
1 =	The subnational tier shares responsibility for a policy with other actors from jurisdictions within the same tier.

11. What are the possible shared policy responsibilities of subnational jurisdictions?

The concepts of self-rule and shared rule are well-established in the federalism and decentralization literature. Self-rule is the authority exercised by a subnational government over citizens within its territorial boundaries. Shared rule is the authority exercised by subnational governments together with the national government over citizens across the statewide territory (Elazar 1987; Hooghe et al. 2016). There are two institutional expressions of shared rule. First, shared rule can be exercised through an upper chamber of national parliament that consists of representatives elected by citizens from or appointed by parliaments (or executives) of subnational jurisdictions. The extent of shared rule that can be exercised through an upper chamber of parliament depends on whether subnational representatives constitute a minority or majority among the total number of representatives. Second, shared rule can be exercised through regular and institutionalized intergovernmental meetings between members of the executives of subnational and national governments. Intergovernmental councils can be policy specific, for example when the education or finance ministers meet, or can be generalist, which often means a peak council of prime ministers that oversees the operation of policy specific councils (Schnabel 2020). The different ways in which shared rule can be exercised lead to four different scores on ACTOR-SH which is a nominal variable that specifies the actor(s) who exercises shared rule (Table 11.1).

The indicator DEPTH-SH measures the extent to which the intergovernmental body, i.e. either an upper chamber of parliament or an intergovernmental council—takes collective decisions and the extent to which the intergovernmental body determines the content of those decisions (Table 11.2). The coding rules for DEPTH-SH are adjusted to the type of intergovernmental body but the scores resulting from both types of coding can be rank ordered on the basis of the extent to which an upper chamber or an intergovernmental council can impact national policy.

An upper chamber can provide input on national policy through, for example asking questions or during a debate with a minister. These parliamentary sessions do not have to end up with a decision taken by the upper chamber nor do they require a national minister to amend national law (score of 1). An upper chamber of parliament can take a decision regarding national law and reject part or the whole law which sends a clear signal to a national minister but does not require a national minister to act accordingly (score of 2). A national minister needs to retract, amend or draft a new national law in case upper chamber has veto power (score of 3).

Table 11.1. Indicator ACTOR-SH.

ACTOR-SH: <i>The actor from a subnational tier who shares the competences for a policy.</i>	
0 =	No subnational actor is involved.
1 =	Subnational representatives in an upper chamber of parliament who collectively represent a minority.
2 =	Subnational representatives in an upper chamber of parliament who collectively represent a majority.
3 =	Members of the executives of subnational jurisdictions.
4 =	Chairs of the executives of subnational jurisdictions.

Table 11.2. Indicator DEPTH-SH.

DEPTH-SH: <i>The extent to which a responsibility for a policy is shared.</i>	
0 =	Upper chamber of parliament does not discuss nor decide national policy. Representatives from subnational tiers and national governments do not meet and do not take collective decisions.
1 =	Upper chamber of parliament provides input but does not decide on national policy. Representatives from subnational tiers and national governments meet to exchange information and provide input but they do not take collective decisions.
2 =	Upper chamber of parliament decides on but cannot veto national policy. Representatives from subnational tiers and national governments meet to take collective decisions without legally binding authority.
3 =	Upper chamber of parliament can veto national policy. Representatives from subnational tiers and national governments meet to take collective decisions with legally binding authority.

Regional and federal ministers can meet to exchange information to learn from each other's Covid-19 governmental responses or to discuss possible Covid-19 responses. This may result in some degree of harmonization and coordination of Covid-19 responses, but regional and federal executive members decide for themselves what, if any, legal actions will follow from the intergovernmental meeting (score of 1). Intergovernmental meetings can also result in an explicitly expressed commitment—often in the form of a declaration or press release—to adhere to the same policy objectives and to coordinate and harmonize regional and federal policies (score of 2). In some cases, an explicitly expressed commitment may include the adoption of a similar set of commonly agreed rules laid down in national and/or regional legislation (score of 3).

ACTOR-SH and DEPTH-SH are meant to measure shared rule in the Covid-19 governmental responses and therefore we start coding on the day when an intergovernmental council meets or when an upper chamber holds a session to discuss Covid-19 related policy. Scores are applied to whole time periods during which meetings or sessions have taken place. Scores end from the date when Covid-19 governmental responses are retracted or terminated. The country profiles will provide further detail on the time periods for which shared rule will be scored.

In many instances, it is practically not feasible to connect intergovernmental meetings to specific national laws or specific policies/regulations. For example, secondary sources often mention when and for what purpose subnational and national representatives met but which (parts of) national or regional legislation resulted from decisions taken in those meetings is often not mentioned. The involvement of an upper chamber in national legislation can be very reliably traced in case national law requires the approval or consent of an upper chamber. From the contents of a national law, one could assess DEPTH-SH exercised by an upper chamber for differential governmental responses. However, we refrain from coding shared rule across the full list of Covid-19 governmental responses because it cannot be systematically, reliably, and validly done for shared rule exercised through intergovernmental meetings.

In addition, shared rule regarding Covid-19 governmental responses is most likely limited to a small subset the countries (8 out of 31) and subnational tiers (8 out of 68) included in our dataset. Subnational tiers elect or appoint representatives of the upper chamber in five countries.¹⁷ Regular intergovernmental meetings between regional and national executives take place in seven countries which includes four of the five countries in which the upper chamber is elected or appointed by subnational tiers.¹⁸ Considerations of the limited relevance of shared rule among the sample of countries included in the dataset, the challenges to validly and reliably code intergovernmental meetings, and a need to keep the research feasible we decided to code ACTOR-SH and DEPTH-SH for time periods during the Covid-19 crisis rather than for each Covid-19 governmental response separately.

Scores of 0 on ACTOR-SH and DEPTH-SH does not mean that here has been no shared rule between subnational and national governments at all. For example, the chair of the national level safety region (*Veiligheidsberaad*) in the Netherlands is elected by and from the 25 chairs of the safety regions whose members consist of the mayors of 342 municipalities. The chair of the national level safety region was an advisory member of the ministerial committee Covid-19 which decided on the Covid-19 national

¹⁷ Austria, Belgium, Germany, the Netherlands, and Spain score 0,5 on the multilateral law making indicator (L2) of the Regional Authority Index that taps whether regional governments designate representatives in a national legislature (Hooghe et al. 2016; Shair-Rosenfield et al. 2021).

¹⁸ Austria, Belgium, Germany, Italy, Spain, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom score 1 or 2 on the multilateral executive control indicator of the Regional Authority Index (Hooghe et al. 2016; Shair-Rosenfield et al. 2021).

government responses.¹⁹ Hence, there was thus an exchange of information between subnational and national government before the statewide executive adopted Covid-19 responses. However, this input can be qualified to be very indirect –one representative for 25/342 safety regions/municipalities who assumed an advisor role—to such an extent that it hardly qualifies as shared rule.

Another example of (type of) shared rule that is not captured by ACTOR-SH and DEPTH-SH –nor INDIRECT-SF—concerns the decision by the Norwegian national government to apply regulations in certain regions. Some of these decisions were requested by the municipalities from the region whose request resulted from a meeting between representatives from these municipalities with the region’s *statsforvalter* (centrally appointed ‘prefect’) and representatives from several national agencies. This was done for efficiency reasons and for transparency and clarity because one national decision that applies to a particular region prevented the municipalities from taking decisions each by themselves.²⁰ However, there have also been instances whereby a minority of municipalities was opposed to a decision by the national government to impose regulations on a particular region.²¹ It is practically infeasible to trace this kind of horizontal and vertical shared-rule for each territorially differentiated decision (see also §5). The practical infeasibility arises from the sheer number of territorially differentiated regulations but also from the informal nature and non-transparent nature (i.e. there is no systematic record) for many of these meetings.

¹⁹ <https://www.veiligheidsberaad.nl/covid-19/>

²⁰ <https://www.regjeringen.no/no/dokumentarkiv/regjeringen-solberg/aktuelt-regjeringen-solberg/hod/nyheter/2021ny/forlengelse-av-regionale-tiltak-for-en-rekke-kommuner-i-vestfold-og-telemark/id2842210/>

²¹ <https://www.regjeringen.no/no/dokumentarkiv/regjeringen-solberg/aktuelt-regjeringen-solberg/hod/nyheter/2021ny/innforer-strengere-regionale-tiltak-i-hele-viken/id2838828/>

12. Draft coding scheme for tracing subnational authority in governmental policy.

Table 12.1. Draft coding scheme for self-rule.

SELF-RULE		The authority exercised by a subnational jurisdiction over policy within its territory			
ACTOR-SF	The actor from a subnational tier who exercises the competences for a policy.	0-6	0	No subnational actor is involved.	
			1	An executive appointed by the central government.	
			2	An executive appointed by the regional government.	
			3	An indirectly elected executive appointed by the assembly.	
			4	An executive directly elected by citizens.	
			5	An indirectly elected assembly with representatives (s)elected from jurisdictions within the subnational tier.	
DEPTH-SF	The extent to which a subnational tier is responsible for a policy.	0-4	0	No or very weak authoritative competencies.	
			1	Responsible for the implementation of higher tier rules and the competence to decide whether criteria specified in higher tier rules do (not) apply.	
			2	Responsible for the implementation of higher tier rules and the competence to decide on additional rules.	
			3	Responsible for the implementation of higher tier rules and the competence to decide on additional rules and to amend higher tier rules including deciding to (not) enforce national rules.	
			4	Authoritative (decision-making) competences for rules.	
INDIRECT-SF	The extent to which a subnational tier shares responsibility for a policy.	0-1	0	The subnational tier does not share responsibility for a policy.	
			0.5	The subnational tier shares responsibility for a policy with other actors and it cannot veto decisions.	
			1	The subnational tier shares responsibility for a policy with other actors from jurisdictions within the same tier.	

Table 12.2. Draft coding scheme for shared rule.

SHARED RULE		The authority collectively exercised by subnational and national governments over national policy.		
ACTOR-SH	The actor from a subnational tier who shares the competences for national policy.	0-4	0	No subnational actor is involved.
			1	Subnational representatives in an upper chamber of parliament who collectively represent a minority.
			2	Subnational representatives in an upper chamber of parliament who collectively represent a majority.
			3	Members of the executives of subnational jurisdictions.
			4	Chairs of the executives of subnational jurisdictions.
DEPTH-SH	The extent to which a responsibility for national policy is shared.	0-3	0	Upper chamber of parliament does not discuss nor decide national policy.
			1	Upper chamber of parliament provides input but does not decide on national policy.
			2	Upper chamber of parliament decides on but cannot veto national policy.
			3	Upper chamber of parliament can veto national policy.
			0	Representatives from subnational tiers and national governments do not meet.
			1	Representatives from subnational tiers and national governments meet to exchange information and provide input but they do not take collective decisions.
			2	Representatives from subnational tiers and national governments meet to take collective decisions without legally binding authority.
			3	Representatives from subnational tiers and national governments meet to take collective decisions with legally binding authority.

13. Why are there different scores for subnational tiers and countries?

The unit of analysis in the draft coding scheme is a subnational government tier and scores on ACTOR-SF, DEPTH-SF, INDIRECT-SF, ACTOR-SH, and DEPTH-SH are assigned to subnational tiers. In some instances, a tier consists of two or three different types of jurisdictions (see Table 8.1), and these are separately coded in instances when their authority in the Covid-19 governmental responses is different (i.e. there is asymmetry in authority). To obtain a score for a subnational tier we weigh the jurisdictional type (j) scores by their relative population shares, we multiply with INDIRECT-SF to account for authority that has indirectly exercised (see §10). Then we sum the jurisdictional type scores for each policy or Covid-19 governmental response (k) and we subsequently sum policy scores and divide the sum by the total number of policies.

$$\text{Subnational self rule score} = \frac{\sum_k^n \sum_j^n \text{Depth SF}_j * \text{Indirect SF}_j * \text{Pop. share}_j}{N_k}$$

$$\text{Subnational shared rule score} = \sum_j^n \text{Depth SH}_j * \text{Pop. share}_j$$

We derive self-rule scores that include all 32 Covid-19 governmental responses, but the availability of policy specific DEPTH-SF and INDIRECT-SF scores enable researchers to focus on only one policy or to use two or more Covid-19 governmental responses for deriving subnational tier self-rule scores. All 31 but six countries have two or more subnational tiers (see Table 8.1). In many countries, different subnational tiers were involved in the Covid-19 responses and the overall authority exercised by subnational governments requires the aggregation of scores of two or more subnational tiers. To derive country scores, we sum the scores of the subnational tiers (i) and we divide the sum by the number of subnational tiers.

$$\text{Country self rule score} = \frac{\sum_i^n \text{Subnational self rule score}_i}{N_i}$$

$$\text{Country shared rule score} = \frac{\sum_i^n \text{Subnational shared rule score}_i}{N_i}$$

Overall authority scores can be derived by adding self-rule and shared rule scores. All types of scores can be adjusted by selecting scores on ACTOR-SF and ACTOR-SH. For example, one can be interested in tracing subnational authority exercised by assemblies and executives. Separate self-rule and shared rule scores for assemblies and executives can be calculated by respectively selecting scores 1-4 versus 5-6 on ACTOR-SF scores 1-2 versus 3-4 on ACTOR-SH.

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One of the main considerations to take into account when calculating scores is whether or not to include subnational tiers (*i*), jurisdictional types (*j*), or policies (*k*) that have only or mostly zero scores. The self-rule and shared rule scores we have calculated includes all subnational tiers (and types) listed in Table 8.1 and all Covid-19 governmental responses listed in §4. The rationale for including all 32 policies is that most countries had a policy in place some time during the Covid-19 crisis but start and end dates differ. Hence, overall subnational authority in the Covid-19 governmental responses should take into account cross-sectional and temporal variation across policy areas. Scores can be calculated for each day during 2020-2022. In addition, including more policy specific indicators contributes to the validity and reliability of aggregate scores.

The rationale for including all subnational tiers (and jurisdictional types) is that the (non-)involvement of more tiers is indicative for the overall level of (de)centralization in the Covid-19 governmental responses. In other words, involving only one subnational tier whereas there are three subnational tiers within a country can be conceived to be a relatively centralized response compared to the involvement of one subnational tier in a country that has only one subnational tier. Obviously, these rationales are based on the research objective to produce scores that are indicative of overall levels of (de)centralization in Covid-19 governmental responses in the country as a whole during the complete time span of the Covid-19 crisis. Depending on specific research purposes, one may prefer different operationalizations.

14. Why is the draft coding scheme applied to a corpus of legal documents?

The draft coding scheme is applied to a corpus of legal documents, i.e. rules laid down in decisions taken by (sub)national governments that have legally binding force. These often include among others, laws, ministerial decrees, ministerial orders, mandates, and so forth. Legal documents enable a valid and reliable coding of formal authority exercised by subnational jurisdictions because legal documents specify which actor can decide on which rules. In addition, legal documents clearly specify the start and end dates during which an actor can decide on rules.

It is important to note that, even though legal documents clearly specify what authority can be exercised by which actor, often pre-knowledge of multilevel government, including the allocation of policy provision responsibilities across tiers of government, is necessary for valid and reliable coding. For example, in Denmark from August 1, 2020 until March 1, 2021, ‘owners’ of educational institutions were responsible for the re-opening and closing of educational institutions according to the guidelines on prevention and containment of the spread of the virus set out by the national health authorities (Law Nos 1103/2020 and 1877/2020). Hence, municipalities and regions were involved in the Covid-19 governmental response to the extent they own educational institutions. Danish municipal councils are responsible for the construction/maintenance of buildings and hiring and paying staff for child care institutions and primary and lower secondary schools (see LAI-country profile Denmark). Regional councils are responsible for special education for children with special needs (e.g. blind and deaf children) and they receive earmarked funds for these special schools from the national government (Council of Europe 2022).

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Non-legal governmental documents such as press releases and websites dedicated to Covid-19 measures provide for an important source for the coding by the OxCRGT. These sources provide for a valid and reliable base for coding the restrictiveness of the Covid-19 governmental responses. That is, these sources clearly specify which rules regarding topics such as group gathering sizes, curfews, facemask requirements, etc. are in place and during what time period, but they do often do not specify which actor has taken the decision. For example, a website managed by the national government may mention that particular containment and closure policies are enforced in specific set of municipalities, but it does not mention whether this the result of a national decision or multiple municipal decisions.²²

To increase the validity and reliability of our coding primarily based on primary sources (i.e. legal documents), we do make extensive use of various types of secondary sources, including governmental websites and press releases as well as academic literature (books, book chapters, and academic journal articles). Primary and secondary sources are listed in the country profiles. The country profiles include an overview of the subnational authority in the Covid-19 governmental responses and detail the information that underlies the coding and scores. Thereby, the country profiles greatly enhance the transparency, validity and reliability of the coding.

15. Is the draft coding scheme feasible?

The application of the proposed draft coding scheme implies the development of a dataset with more than 2 million observations. The involvement of 68 subnational tiers (ACTOR-SF/SH and DEPTH-SF/SH and INDIRECT-SF) in 32 Covid-19 responses will be traced on a daily basis for three years (2020-2022: 1,069 days) which totals up to 2,326,144 observations. The scope of the dataset has already been limited by deciding (1) to exclude socio-economic policy/governmental responses (see §6), (2) not to code territorially differentiated governmental responses (see §5), and (3) not to apply the shared rule indicator to each of the Covid-19 governmental responses separately (see §11). In addition, we will prioritize coding national governmental responses before we will code sub-national Covid-19 governmental responses for seven countries, and before we will code shared rule in eight countries (see §11). This coding may be included in version 2.0 of the dataset.

The feasibility of the application of the draft coding scheme is further significantly enhanced by the incidence of ‘authority regimes’ laid down in few national laws specifically designed to cope with the Covid-19 crisis. For example, many countries adopted a Covid-19 law that specified which actor could decide whether and what kind of regulations were put in place for a wide range of containment and closure and health system policies. Often, subnational tiers were tasked with the implementation of the rules or were given the authority to apply stricter rules or to lift national rules, often depending on local conditions such as infection rates. In several instances, a ‘traffic-light’ or ‘color’ scheme was specified in a national law whereby each ‘color’ stood for a particular set of rules regarding containment and closure and health system policies. For example, five persons could meet when the ‘traffic light’ was set on red whereas ten citizens could meet when the ‘traffic light’ was set on yellow. National governments could quickly adjust the set of rules according to surges and declines in infection rates and according to

²² This example is based on the website ‘timeline: the governments management of the corona situation’ managed by the Norwegian national government: <https://www.regjeringen.no/no/tema/Koronasituasjonen/tidslinje-koronaviruset/id2692402/>

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territorially heterogeneous infection rates. Subnational tiers could do that as well when a national law granted them the authority to adjust the ‘traffic light’ in their jurisdictions.

Often, these ‘framework laws’ specify that only one or few subnational tiers and only one or few actors within those tiers have some authority whereas the other subnational tiers and actors do not play any significant (legally specified) role in the Covid-19 governmental responses. For example, municipalities in the Netherlands (*gemeenten*) and Norway (*kommuner*) clearly played a significant role during most of the Covid-19 crisis whereas the counties (*provincies/fylkeskommuner*) did not. In other words, the counties receive many zeros in the dataset. It is nevertheless important to trace the non-involvement of subnational tiers because this may reveal important cross-national (and potentially over time) variation in the involvement of type of subnational tiers. For example, in Austria both the states (*Länder*) and the districts (*Bezirke/Statutarstädte*) played an important role during the Covid-19 crisis but municipalities (*Gemeinden*) did not. The different involvement of subnational tiers between Austria and Norway and the Netherlands might be explained by differences in policy capacity of municipalities between the countries which subsequently can be ascribed to differences in size (population and budget) and/or policy portfolios.

The presence of ‘authority regimes’ and ‘framework laws’ makes the coding much more feasible because one only needs to know when a set of scores need to start and end. The start and dates of regulatory regimes (i.e. a national law, or a ‘traffic light’ or ‘color scheme’ setting) is often laid down in national law, a ministerial decree or another decision with legally binding force. Thus, once a set of scores for a particular ‘authority regime’ has been set, one can copy-and-paste this set of scores from begin date to end date on the basis on one or few legal documents.

16. Are the indicators generalizable to other (types of) crises?

The draft coding scheme can be applied to any type of crisis, but the selection of policies may need to be adjusted. ACTOR refers to the specific body within a subnational tier that exercises authority whereas DEPTH and INDIRECT tap the depth of the exercised authority. These three indicators can be applied to one or more policies and the comparability and generalizability of evaluations of subnational authority involvement in governmental responses ultimately depends on the scope of policies that are included in the assessment. The draft coding scheme explicitly defines a range of Covid-19 governmental responses (§4) for which ACTOR, DEPTH, and INDIRECT will be assessed. Governmental responses towards other (types of) crises may be different with varying degrees. For example, weather crises (snow, wind, flooding) are relatively frequent events and often necessitate the closing of educational institutions, but ad hoc vaccination policy is only required for crises that involve a new virus or pandemic.

The Covid-19 crisis may have invoked national rather than subnational responses because it was a pandemic with important national and supra-national externalities. Governmental responses may be much more localized in case of crises with externalities at the subnational level. We apply the draft coding scheme to whole subnational tiers, and we do not evaluate each and every jurisdictional decision that deviates from a national regulatory framework to keep the coding exercise feasible (see §5). But ACTOR and DEPTH can be easily applied to a single or few subnational tiers instead of evaluating all jurisdictions within a tier by, for example, replacing the words ‘subnational tier’ with ‘municipality or region’ in the coding criteria.

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17. Which research questions can (not) be addressed with the coding scheme?

The coding scheme defines a set of 32 policies (Covid-19 governmental responses; see §4) for which ACTOR, DEPTH, and INDIRECT are assessed on a daily basis for three years starting from January 1, 2020. Thereby, the application of the coding scheme will result in a detailed account of subnational authority in the governmental responses during the Covid-19 crisis. The coding scheme is developed with two main research objectives in mind. First, to be able to study the causes for a (de-)decentralized crisis response and, two, to study the impacts of a (de-)centralized crisis response. An application of the coding scheme enables addressing both research objectives, but one important caveat should be kept in mind. The scores resulting from an application of the coding scheme relies very much on the range of policies to which it is applied to (§4) whereas policy scope is one out of several sub-indicators of other measurements for local and regional authority.

Regarding the causes for a (de-)centralized governmental crisis response, one may be interested in testing the hypothesis that countries that are (de-)centralized prior a crisis will also tend to have a (de-)centralized governmental response during the crisis. This hypothesis can be tested by observing whether higher scores on the Local Autonomy Index (LAI) and Regional Authority Index (RAI) are associated with higher scores on DEPTH. However, subnational authority in the Covid-19 governmental responses might be stronger related to the allocation of policy competences across governmental tiers. For example, regional authority is relatively weak in Denmark and relatively strong in the Netherlands. Regions in Denmark score 7 and Dutch provinces score 17.5 out of a maximum score of 30 and (Figure 7.1). Yet, the involvement of Danish regions in the Covid-19 governmental response is relatively high whereas Dutch provinces were hardly involved. This stark difference can be explained by Danish regions being responsible for providing public health and hospitals but not much else whereas the portfolio of Dutch provinces does not include many policies that were part of the Covid-19 governmental responses.

The RAI, and to a lesser extent the LAI, do not assess authority exercised within particular policies. The RAI codes three broad clusters of ‘economic policy’, ‘cultural-educational policy’ and ‘welfare policy’ and the LAI tracks local government responsibility in education, land use, police, social assistance, public transport, caring functions, health, and housing. Furthermore, none of these measures traces whether a policy is provided by one or jointly by two or more subnational government tiers. Hence, an appropriate understanding of the causes for (de-)centralized crisis responses requires a ‘policy provision decentralization index’ that assesses the ex ante (pre-crisis) allocation of responsibilities for the provision of policies across governmental tiers (Hassan and Schakel 2023).

A similar caveat arises regarding studying the impacts of a (de-)centralized governmental crisis response. For example, research has repeatedly found that trust in local and regional government is (often) higher than trust in national government (Denters 2002; Jedwab and Kincaid 2018) and that trust in levels of government can spill-over between government tiers (Proszowska, Jansen and Denters 2022, 2023). One may therefore hypothesize that trust in government and the perceived legitimacy of governmental responses is relatively higher when subnational governments have been more involved in deciding and implementing the Covid-19 measures. However, both Denmark and the Netherlands experienced a centralization of authority regarding the Covid-19 governmental responses, but this centralization is likely to have been more noticeable for Danish than for Dutch citizens because Danish regions providing public health and hospitals (and not much else) whereas Dutch municipalities and provinces are not much

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involved in the provision of these policies. Hence, the impacts of (de)centralized governmental Covid-19 responses can be theorized to result from the degree to which citizens have experienced a 'shock', i.e. the extent to which governmental crisis responses 'deviated' or were 'unusual' when compared to 'normal' or 'status quo' levels of decentralized policy provision. Hence, in addition to a direct effect, one may also hypothesize an interaction effect with the ex-ante (pre-crisis) decentralization of policy provision responsibilities. Trust in government and the perceived legitimacy of governmental responses may *decline* when a centralized and nationally dominated response is adopted in a country where subnational governments 'normally' have a large role in the provision of policy.

18. References

- CEMR (The Council of European Municipalities and Regions) (2021) Terri report. Territorial, governance, powers, and reforms in Europe. 2021 edition: Focus on local health care systems. Available at: <https://terri.cemr.eu/en/>
- Cheng Cindy, Joan Barceló, Allison Spencer Hartnett, Robert Kubinec, and Luca Messerschmidt (2020) 'Covid-19 government response event dataset (CoronaNet v.1.0),' *Nature Human Behaviour* 4: 756-768.
- Council of Europe (2022) *Local and regional democracy in Denmark*. Strasbourg, France: Council of Europe.
- Denters, Bas (2002) 'Size and political trust: Evidence from Denmark, the Netherlands, Norway, and the United Kingdom,' *Environment and Planning C: Government and Policy* 20: 793-812.
- Greer, Scott L., Elizabeth J. King, Elize Massard da Fonseca, and Andre Peralta-Santos (2020) 'The comparative politics of Covid-19: The need to understand government responses,' *Global Public Health* 15(9): 1413-1416.
- Griglio, Elena (2020) 'Parliamentary oversight under the Covid-19 emergency: Striving against executive dominance,' *The Theory and Practice of Legislation* 8(1-2): 49-70.
- Guderjan, Marius, Ana Herrero, Mario Kölling, Johanna Schnabel, and Alice Valdesalici (2023) Literature review work package 6. Working paper Legitimate Crisis Governance in Multilevel Systems (LEGITIMULT). Available at: <https://legitimult.eu/outputs/working-papers/>
- Hale, Thomas, Noam Angrist, Rafael Goldszmidt, Beatriz Kira, Anna Petherick, Toby Phillips, Samuel Webster, Emily Cameron-Blake, Laura Hallas, Saptarshi Majumdar, and Helen Tatlow (2021) 'A global panel database of pandemic policies (Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker),' *Nature Human Behaviour* 5: 529-538. <https://github.com/OxCGRT/covid-policy-dataset>
- Hassan, Bilal and Arjan H. Schakel (2023) 'Intergovernmental relations during crises: Self-rule and shared rule of local and regional Governments during the Covid-19 crisis in 31 European Countries,' paper presented at the 1st IGCOORD Conference (IGCOORD - CA20123), May 18-19 2023, Budapest, Hungary.
- Hegele, Yvonne Hegele and Johanna Schnabel (2021) 'Federalism and the management of the COVID-19 crisis: centralisation, decentralisation and (non-)coordination,' *West European Politics* 44(5-6): 1052-1076.

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- Hooghe, Liesbet, Gary Marks, Arjan H. Schakel, Sara Niedzwiecki, Sandra Chapman Osterkatz, and Sarah Shair-Rosenfield (2016) *Measuring regional authority. A postfunctionalist theory of governance, Volume I*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Jedwab, Jack and Kincaid, John (eds.) (2018) *Identities, trust, and cohesion in federal systems. Public perspectives*. Kingston, Ontario: McGill University Press.
- Kuhn, Katarina and Irene Morlino (2022) 'Decentralisation in times of crisis: Asset or liability? The case of Germany and Italy during Covid-19,' *Swiss Political Science Review* 28(1): 105-115.
- Ladner, Andreas, Nicolas Keuffer, Harald Baldersheim, Nikos Hlepas. Pawel Swianiewicz, Kristof Steyvers, and Carmen Navarro (2019) *Patterns of local autonomy in Europe*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Ladner, Andreas, Nicolas Keuffer and Alexander Bastianen (2023) 'Local autonomy around the world: The updated and extended Local Autonomy Indec (LAI 2.0),' *Regional & Federal Studies*, doi: 10.1080/13597.566.2023.2267990
- Lozano, Maritza, Michael Atkinson, and Haizhen Mou (2023) 'Democratic accountability in times of crisis: Executive power, fiscal policy and COVID-19.' *Government and Opposition* 58(1): 39-60.
- Maher, Craig S., Trang Hoang, and Anne Hindery (2020) 'Fiscal responses to COVID -19: Evidence from local governments and nonprofits,' *Public Administration Review* 80(4): 644-650.
- Mathieu Edouard, Hannah Ritchie, Lucas Rodés-Guirao, Cameron Appel, Charlie Giattino, Joe Hasell, Bobbie Macdonald, Saloni Dattani, Diana Beltekian, Esteban Ortiz-Ospina and Max Roser (2020) *Coronavirus Pandemic (COVID-19)*. Published online at OurWorldInData.org. Retrieved from: <https://ourworldindata.org/coronavirus>
- Mueller, Sean (2015) *Theorising decentralization. Comparative evidence from sub-national Switzerland*. Colchester: ECPR Press.
- Navarro, Carmena and Francisco Velasco (2022) 'From centralisation to new ways of multi-level coordination: Spain's intergovernmental response to the COVID-19 pandemic,' *Local Government Studies* 48(2): 191-210.
- OECD (2021) *The territorial impact of Covid-19: Managing the crisis and recovery across levels of government*. Paris: OECD.
- Petrov, Jan (2020) 'The COVID-19 emergency in the age of executive aggrandizement: what role for legislative and judicial checks?' *The Theory and Practice of Legislation* 8(1-2): 71-92.
- Porcher Simon (2020) 'Response2covid19, a dataset of governments' responses to Covid-19 all around the world,' *Scientific Data* 7: 423, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-00757-y>
- Porcher Simon (2023) 'A dataset of governments' economic responses to Covid-19,' Data in Brief 47, 109021. <https://github.com/simonporcher/COVID-19-Governments-Responses>
- Posner, Eric A. and Adrian Vermeule (2009) 'Crisis governance in the administrative state: 9/11 and the financial meltdown of 2008,' *Univeristy of Chicago Law Review* 76: 1613-1682.
- Proszowska, Dominika, Jansen, Guido and Denters, Bas (2022) 'On their own turf? The level-spezifity of political trust in multilevel political systems,' *Acta Politica* 57: 510-528.

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- Proszowska, Dominika, Jansen, Guido and Denters, Bas (2023) 'Political trust in a multilevel polity: Patterns of differentiation among more and less politically sophisticated citizens,' *International Review of Administrative Sciences* 89(1): 165-185.
- Rosenthal, Uri, Paul 't Hart, Paul, and M. T. Charles (eds.). (1989) *Coping with crises*. Charles C. Thomas.
- Rozell, Mark J. and Clyde Wilcox (2020) 'Federalism in a time of plague: How federal systems cope with pandemic,' *The American Review of Public Administration* 50(6-7): 519-525.
- Szöcsik, Edina (2023) Literature review and methodology work package 3. Working paper Legitimate Crisis Governance in Multilevel Systems (LEGITIMULT). Available at: <https://legitimult.eu/outputs/working-papers/>
- Shair-Rosenfield, Sarah, Arjan H. Schakel, Sara Niedzwiecki, Gary Marks, and Liesbet Hooghe (2021) 'Language difference and regional authority,' *Regional & Federal Studies* 31(1): 73-97.
- Steytler, Nico (2022) 'Introduction: How federation combat Covid-19,' in Nico Steytler (ed.) *Comparative federalism and Covid-19*, pp.1-12. London: Routledge.
- Toshkov, Dimiter, Brendan Carroll, and Kutsal Yesilkagit (2022) 'Government capacity, societal trust or party preferences: What accounts for the variety of national policy responses to the Covid-19 pandemic in Europe?' *Journal of European Public Policy* 29(7): 1009-1028.
- Warner, Sam, David Richards, Dian Coyle, and Martin J. Smith (2021) 'English devolution and the Covid-19 pandemic: Governing dilemmas in the shadow of the Treasury,' *Political Quarterly* 92(2): 321-330.
- World Health Organization (2005) *International health regulations*. Geneva: World Health Organization.

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19. Appendix: Draft country profile on the Netherlands

There are 342 municipalities and twelve provinces in the Netherlands. Municipalities have competences in public health and crisis management but, during the first year of the Covid-19 crisis (i.e. during 2020) their involvement in the Covid-19 governmental responses was mainly indirect through their representation in 'safety regions'. In the second year of the Covid-19 crisis (i.e. during 2021), municipal mayors were involved directly by having the competence to grant exemptions in individual cases of national rules but only in few Covid-19 governmental responses. Provinces have been indirectly involved soon after the start of the Covid-19 crisis through their representation in an upper chamber of national parliament.

A municipal executive (*burgemeester en wethouders*) consists of several alderman (*wethouders*) elected by the municipal council (*gemeenteraad*) and an indirectly elected mayor (*burgemeester*) who is formally appointed by the central government but selected and nominated by the municipal council. The municipal executive is responsible for fire brigades and fire prevention, medical assistance, disaster response, and crisis management in the municipality (Law No. 27466/2010, Art. 3). The municipal executive is also responsible for the implementation of national policy regarding youth health care, elderly health care, and infectious disease control (Law No. 24705/2008, Arts. 5-6). The mayor takes the lead during times of disasters and crisis.

When a disaster, crisis or epidemic transcends municipal boundaries, the safety region is responsible for managing the disaster, crisis, or epidemic (Law No. 27466/2010, Art. 39).²³ Each municipality is member of a safety region (*veiligheidsregio*) which is responsible, among other competences, for inventorying risks of disasters and crises, the preparation for crisis and disasters, and the establishment and maintenance of a regional fire brigade and a medical assistance organization (Law No. 27466/2010, Arts. 8-10). The board of a safety region consists of the mayors from the municipalities within a safety region and the chair of a safety region is selected and nominated by and from the board and appointed by the central government (Law No. 27466/2010, Art. 11).

The medical assistance organization of a safety region (*geneeskundige hulpverleningsorganisatie in de regio, GHOR*) is responsible for the organization and coordination of hospitals, ambulance services, general practitioners, pharmacies during crises, disasters and epidemics (Law No. 24705/2008, Arts. 14-16).²⁴ Each safety region also sets up a municipal health service (*gemeentelijk gezondheidsdienst, GGD*) which is responsible for public health monitoring, public health education, school doctors, and infectious disease control (Law No. 24705/2008, Arts. 14-16).²⁵ Both the GHOR and GGD are led by a director (*directeur publieke gezondheidszorg*) who is appointed by the board –usually consisting of the municipal

²³ In case of natural disasters and crisis that are regional in scope, the head of the provincial executive (Commissaris van de Koning) can provide instructions to a safety region which are regulated in an official instruction from the national government (Law No. 27466/2010, Arts. 41-42; Law No. 6728/1994, Arts. 5a-5d). However, during the Covid-19 crisis, the national government instructed directly the chairs of the safety regions without using the provincial executives as intermediaries. A temporary Covid-19 law went into effect on December 1, 2020 which specified competences for municipal mayors.

²⁴ <https://ggdghor.nl/home/wat-doet-de-ghor/>

²⁵ <https://ggdghor.nl/home/wat-doet-een-ggd/>

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alderman responsible for public health—in accordance with the board of the safety region (Law No. 24705/2008, Art. 14.3).²⁶

We start coding Covid-19 governmental responses from March 13, 2020, when the chairs of the safety regions were instructed by the minister for medical care and sports (*Minister voor Volksgezondheid en Sport*) to adopt measures through emergency ordinances (*noodverordeningen*). We stop coding Covid-19 governmental responses on May 20, 2022 when the temporary law on Covid-19 measures (*Tijdelijke Wet Maatregelen COVID-19*; Law No. 44337/2020) was not prolonged.²⁷ The Covid-19 virus was classified as a group A infectious disease between January 28, 2020 and January 24, 2024 which meant that certain national provisions could be invoked (Law Nos. 6800/2020 and 15/2024; Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport 2023d).²⁸

Throughout the crisis, decision-making was mostly located at the national level. The prime minister chaired a ministerial committee (*Ministeriële Commissie Crisisbeheersing, MCCb*) which decided on measures prepared by an inter-ministerial crisis management committee (*Interdepartementale Commissie Crisisbeheersing, ICCb*).²⁹ The chairs of the 25 safety regions form the ‘security council’ (*Veiligheidsberaad*) which advises the minister for justice and safety. The chair of the security council is elected by and from the members of the security council (Law No. 27466/2010, Arts. 1 and 38; *Veiligheidsberaad 2017*).³⁰ The chair of the security council could attend as advisory member to both committees (Ministry of Justice and Safety 2020). The member of the ‘security council’ (*Veiligheidsberaad*) responsible for the medical assistance organizations of the 25 safety regions (*portefeuillehouder GHOR*) was a member of a civil servant committee (*Bestuurlijk Afstemmingsoverleg, BAO*) that advised the national government on the Covid-19 measures (Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu 2020).³¹

In June 2020, the national government decided to change the ‘preparation and decision-making structure’. Civil servants prepared decisions in an inter-ministerial director (*Directeurenoverleg Covid-19, DOC*) and civil servant (*Ambtelijke Commissie Covid-19, ACC*) Covid-19 committees and decision-taking took place in a ministerial Covid-19 committee (*Ministeriële Commissie Covid-19, MCC*). The chair of the security council was an advisory member of the ministerial Covid-19 committee.³²

The Covid-19 virus was classified as a group A infectious disease on 28 January 2020 which meant that certain provision in the public health care law were invoked (Law No. 6800/2020). Between March 13, 2020 and December 1, 2020, when the first temporary law on Covid-19 measures (Law No. 44337/2020) was adopted, the national government decided on the Covid-19 governmental responses (Law No. 24705/2008, Arts 6.4 and 7.1). During this period, the minister for medical care and sport instructed the 25 safety regions to implement the measures through emergency ordinances (Law Nos 24706/2008, Art 7 and 27466/2010, Art 39). The first instructions were provided on March 13, 2020 and the last on

²⁶ <https://ggdghor.nl/directeuren-publieke-gezondheid/>

²⁷ Timelines of the Covid-19 measures are available at: <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/onderwerpen/coronavirus-tijdlijn> and <https://www.rivm.nl/gedragsonderzoek/tijdlijn-van-coronamaatregelen-2020>

²⁸ The decision to renounce the A-status of Covid-19 was taken on June 16, 2023 (Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport 2023d).

²⁹ <https://www.nctv.nl/actueel/nieuws/2020/03/09/nationale-crisisstructuur-actief-voor-coronavirus>

³⁰ <https://www.veiligheidsberaad.nl/voorzitter-veiligheidsberaad/>

³¹ <https://www.veiligheidsberaad.nl/covid-19/> The BAO also includes representatives from the association of Dutch municipalities (*Vereniging van Nederlandse Gemeenten, VNG*).

³² <https://www.veiligheidsberaad.nl/covid-19/>

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November 18, 2020 (Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport 2020a-ac) and the security council provided 'model emergency ordinances' which the safety regions could use.³³ The final advice from the security council concerned the withdrawal of the last emergency ordinance of November 18, 2020 as of December 1, 2020 (Veiligheidsraad 2020a-j).³⁴

During the period between March 13, 2020 and December 1, 2020, the chairs of the 25 safety regions assumed all competences of the municipal mayors granted by the law on safety regions (Law No. 24705/2008).³⁵ The chairs of the safety regions were given the authority to (Veiligheidsraad 2020a-j):

- (1) Designate areas and locations where people were prohibited to be (including curfews). A prohibition could not be applied to residents of areas and locations and to people who carried out necessary work in the areas and locations (Art 2.5). Explanatory memorandums to the model emergency ordinances mention that chair of safety regions could make use of these powers in relation to any area or location (including retail, restaurants, bars, camping sites, parks, swimming pools, etc. but not educational institutions and public health organizations) in case there were indications that the 1.5 meter distance between people could not be complied with, when problems with public transport were to be expected, or when a local outburst of infections had taken place in a location.
- (2) Terminate or limit public transport in consultation with the provider and when the provider was not able to ensure a 1.5 meter distance between persons. The termination could not unnecessarily hinder the mobility of persons working in vital processes or transport that in other ways was important for the mobility in the country (Art 2.6/2.7).
- (3) Decide on exceptions to which the rules would not apply and within the instructions provided by the minister and the provisions laid down in national law (Art 3.1).
- (4) Appoint officers/supervisors who were responsible for compliance to emergency ordinance (Art. 4.2)
- (5) Grant permission to zoo's, nature parks, and amusement parks to open if they submitted a plan which shows that measures had been taken to guarantee a distance of 1.5 meters between persons and the burden on the mobility system (public transport) remained acceptable (Art. 2.1i; from April 24, 2020).
- (6) Grant permission to meetings organized by an educational institution, student sport association, or study association if certain conditions are met such as small scale, no alcoholic beverages, and provided that the meeting did not take place between 10.00 pm and 6.00 am (Art. 2.1a/2.14; from August 10, 2020).
- (7) Determine the maximum number of people that could be present in public areas such as libraries, museums, monuments, zoo's, amusement parks, in consultation with the organization and while taking into account the surface of the location and the requirement of having at least 1.5 meters between visitors. Visitors could only be present in the public area after reserving a time slot (Art. 2.1.7; from October 14, 2020).

³³ The ministerial instructions (*aanwijzingen*) are obtained via <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten>

³⁴ The model emergency ordinances are obtained via <https://www.veiligheidsberaad.nl/>

³⁵ The emergency ordinances of the 25 safety regions can be downloaded from <https://lokaleregelgeving.overheid.nl/>. In what follows, we describe the competences of the chair of the safety regions and the municipal mayors described in the model emergency ordinances. We verified this information with the emergency ordinances of one of the safety regions (*Veiligheids en Gezondheidsregio Gelderland Midden*).

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Mayors had very limited competences and they could:

- (1) Grant permits for events, music and pop concerts in case organizers presented plans that complied with the rules laid down in the emergency ordinance (Veiligheidsregio 2020e, Art 2.1; from July 1, 2020).
- (2) Declare a business to be a 'morning food and drink facility' which allowed a business to open at 4.00 am instead of 6.00 am (Veiligheidsregio 2020g, Art 2.6; from September 20, 2020).

The competences granted to the chairs of the safety regions and the mayors ended on December 1, 2020, when a temporary law on Covid-19 measures (Law No. 44337/2020) was adopted. This law replaced the need to adopt emergency ordinances by 25 safety regions on the instructions provided by the national government.³⁶ The temporary Covid-19 law was extended four times throughout 2021 and was annulled from May 20, 2022 onwards after the upper chamber of parliament did not approve a fifth extension on May 17, 2022 (Law Nos. 93/2021, 232/2021, 393/2021, 549/2021, and 76/2022).³⁷

The temporary law on Covid-19 measures added a chapter to the law on public health (chapter 5a in Law No. 24705/2008) that was entitled 'temporary provisions to combat the Covid-19 epidemic'. This chapter detailed the content of the Covid-19 measures decided by the national government and laid down in 'ministerial regulations' (*ministeriële regeling*; Law No. 62031/2020). This made it possible for the national government to act swiftly in response to changing circumstances because adopting a ministerial regulation does not require the involvement of parliament or other governmental body than the minister.³⁸ However, revisions were only decided after approval of the ministerial council (*Ministerraad*) or with the consent of two or more ministers.

The law transferred the powers granted by the law on safety regions from the chair of the safety region to the mayor (Law No. 24705/2008, Art. 58d.3; Law No. 44337/2020, Memorie van Toelichting (MvT), 4.3). The mayor was given the specific competence to grant the following three types of exemptions after having consulted the municipal health service (*gemeentelijk gezondheidsdienst, GGD*) and taking into consideration the type of location, type of activity, and the number of persons (Law No. 24705/2008, Art. 58e; Vereniging voor Nederlandse Gemeenten 2020):

- (1) An exemption to a national rule stipulating that a group gathering cannot exceed a maximum size at a particular place (Art. 58g.1). Several types of groups gatherings were exempt from these national rules on maximum group size such as religious gatherings, elections, public demonstrations, etc. (Art. 58g.2).
- (2) An exemption to a national rule stipulating that a public place should remained closed or can only open under certain conditions such as hygiene measures or the requirement to reserve a time slot (Art. 58h.1). Several types of public spaces were exempt from these national rules on public spaces such as court houses and meeting locations of democratically elected bodies such as municipal and provincial councils (Art. 58h.2).

³⁶ <https://www.veiligheidsberaad.nl/covid-19/>

³⁷ <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/onderwerpen/coronavirus-covid-19/hoer-gaat-nederland-om-met-het-coronavirus/coronawet-vervangt-noodverordeningen#:~:text=Op%2017%20mei%202022%20ging,de%20tijdelijke%20coronawet%20niet%20meer.>

³⁸ The temporary rules for Covid-19 measures (*Tijdelijke regeling maatregelen covid-19*; Law No. 62031/2020) was amended 74 times between December 1, 2020 and May 20, 2022 when the temporary Covid-19 law was annulled.

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- (3) An exemption to a national rule stipulating that an event cannot take place or can only take place under certain conditions such as hygiene measures or a maximum number of attendees (Art. 58i).

The explanatory memorandum to the temporary Covid-19 law mentioned that mayors should apply their competences with restraint (Law No. 44337/2020, Memorie van Toelichting (MvT)). The mayor was also tasked with the enforcement of the ministerial regulations (Arts. 58k-58n and 58u) and could be asked to designate locations which could provide care twenty-four hours and seven days a week for children who required special care or children from parents with crucial jobs (Art. 58r.3). In addition, the mayor could be asked to provide a minister with information and statistics necessary for deciding ministerial regulations (Art. 58s).

Finally, the mayors could also be given the competence to grant exemptions in relation to other Covid-19 measures—such as hygiene measures, personal protective equipment, contact professions, use of publicly accessible sanitary facilities, and overnight accommodations—if it was determined in those rules in the ministerial regulations (Law No. 24705/2008, Art. 58j). We have not found additional competences to mayors in the 74 revisions of the temporary rules for Covid-19 measures (*Tijdelijke regeling maatregelen covid-19*; Law No. 62031/2020) between December 1, 2020 and May 20, 2022 when the temporary Covid-19 law was annulled.

The temporary provisions to combat the Covid-19 epidemic included in the chapter in the law on public health (chapter 5a in Law No. 24705/2008) were revised several times but the competences granted to the mayor remained very similar.³⁹ From 1 June 2021 onwards, a ministerial regulation could specify that the mayor can grant an individual exception in relation to the obligation of home quarantine after international travel or the requirements in relation to a quarantine declaration (Art. 58nc.4). In addition, the mayor was granted the competence to fine individuals who were in breach with the home quarantine rules (Art. 58v).

The role of the chairs of the safety regions was significantly reduced when the temporary law on Covid-19 measures (Law No. 44337/2020) went into force on December 1, 2020. The chairs remained formally responsible for combating an infectious disease of type A (Law No. 24705/2008, Art. 6.4) but this responsibility is, in practice and also during non-crisis times, mainly executed by the director for public health, who heads the municipal health service (GGD) and medical assistance organization (GHOR). Similarly, the chairs of the safety regions remained formally responsible for crisis communication (Law No. 27466/2010, Arts. 7 and 39.1) but, in practice, the national government took up this responsibility because the minister for public health was primarily responsible for the Covid-19 measures (Veiligheidsberaad 2020k). The main task of the chairs of the safety regions concerned the provision of information delivered by the mayors to the minister of public health (Law No. 24705/2008, Art. 58s). The minister could decide that the chairs of safety regions could exercise a competence granted by law to a mayor, but the minister did not make use of this possibility (Law No. 24705/2008, Art. 58d).

³⁹ We code the following revised versions of the law on public health: 9 January 2021, 22 February 2021, 1 June 2021, 24 June 2021, 1 July 2021, 17 July 2021, 1 September 2021, 1 December 2021, 4 February 2022, 1 March 2022, and 20 May 2022 (temporary law on Covid-19 measures was not prolonged).

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During non-crisis times, the minister for health and sports is responsible for directing and coordinating a vaccination program and the RIVM is tasked by the minister for the execution of a vaccination program which is implemented by the municipal health service (*gemeentelijk gezondheidsdienst, GGD*) in safety regions (Law No. 24705/2008, Art. 6b.2-5). The municipal health service is also responsible for source and contact and tracing (Law No. 24705/2008, Art. 6.1c). The 25 directors (*directeur publieke gezondheid*) of the municipal health services (GGD) and medical assistance organizations (GHOR) have set up *GGD GHOR Nederland* which is an national association which provided help and advice to the GGDs and GHORs in the execution of their tasks and which voices the interests of the GGDs and GHORs. *GGD GHOR Nederland* also performed these functions during the Covid-19 crisis.⁴⁰ For example, the *GGD GHOR Nederland* owns the IT-system for Corona-tests and the organization collaborated regularly with the ministry for public health during the Covid-19 crisis.

In a letter to *GGD GHOR Nederland*, the directors of the municipal health services were tasked directly by the minister for medical care and sports to organize and implement a Covid-19 vaccination program starting in January 2021 (Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport 2020ad, 2021a-k, 2022a-g, 2023a-c).⁴¹ Source and contact tracing regarding the Covid-19 virus was also the responsibility of the municipal health service under the guidance of the national institute for health and environment (*Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu, RIVM*) (Law No. 62031/2020; Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport 2021a-k, 2022a-g, 2023a-c).⁴² In addition, the municipal health services were responsible for the organization and implementation of a testing program for Covid-19, including setting up test locations. There were no legal provisions on testing programs and the minister concluded a covenant on testing policy with the 25 municipal health services and *GGD GHOR Nederland* on January 21, 2021. Importantly, the covenant established a steering group for the national test capacity coordination structure (*Stuurgroep Landelijke Coördinatiestructuur Testcapaciteit, LCT*) with representatives from each of the 25 municipal health services and the ministry for health who had to be delegated the competence to take decisions on behalf of the organizations they represented (Law No. 3656/2021, Art. 1.1). The 25 municipal health services and *GGD GHOR Nederland* have been responsible for co-deciding and implementing the testing policy until March 17, 2023 when the test locations of the municipal health services were closed (Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport 2021a-k, 2022a-g, 2023a-c).⁴³

The upper chamber of national parliament (*Eerste Kamer*) is elected by the members of the assemblies of the twelve provinces (*provincies*) and it has veto rights on all national laws (but no right of amendment) and it can ask ministers written questions.⁴⁴ The upper chamber has been asking written questions, filing motions, and debating and deciding on national laws in relation to Covid-19 governmental measures since March 31, 2020.⁴⁵ The temporary law on Covid-19 measures (Law No. 44337/2020), effective on December 1, 2020, added a chapter to the law on public health (chapter 5a in Law No. 24705/2008) that was entitled ‘temporary provisions to combat the Covid-19 epidemic’. In this chapter, it was specified that national regulations in relation to safe distance and other rules of conduct had to be sent to both chambers of parliament (Law No. 24705/2008, Art. 58f.2). In addition, the minister for public health was

⁴⁰ <https://ggdghor.nl/home/over-ggd-ghor-nederland/>

⁴¹ <https://ggdghor.nl/onderwerp/infectieziektebestrijding/coronavirus/vaccinatie-tegen-coronavirus/>

⁴² <https://ggdghor.nl/onderwerp/infectieziektebestrijding/coronavirus/bron-en-contactonderzoek/> and <https://lci.rivm.nl/richtlijnen/covid-19> and <https://lci.rivm.nl/richtlijnen/covid-19-vaccinatie>

⁴³ <https://ggdghor.nl/onderwerp/infectieziektebestrijding/coronavirus/testen-covid-19/>

⁴⁴ https://www.eerstekamer.nl/begrip/taken_en_positie_eerste_kamer

⁴⁵ https://www.eerstekamer.nl/trefwoord/covid_19

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required to send, on a monthly basis, an overview of the national measures, the reasons for those measures, and a prognosis on the prolongation of the measures (Law No. 24705/2008, Art. 58s).⁴⁶

Primary sources

[Laws were downloaded from: <https://wetten.overheid.nl/>]

- Netherlands (1994) 'Law No. 6728/1994. Ambstrinstructie commissaris van de koning,' August 15, 1994.
- Netherlands (2008) 'Law No. 24705/2008. Wet publieke gezondheid.' November 18, 2008.
- Netherlands (2010) 'Law No. 27466/2010. Wet van 11 februari 2010, houdende bepalingen over de brandweezorg, de rampenbestrijding, de crisisbeheersing en de geneeskundige hulpverlening (Wet veiligheidsregio's).' June 24, 2010.
- Netherlands (2020) 'Law No. 6800/2020. Regeling van de Minister voor Medische Zorg van 28 januari 2020, kenmerk 1643096-201442-PG, ex artikel 20 van de Wet publieke gezondheid (Regeling 2019-nCoV).' January 28, 2020.
- Netherlands (2020) 'Law No. 44337/2020. Tijdelijke bepalingen in verband met maatregelen ter bestrijding van de epidemie van covid-19 voor de langere termijn (Tijdelijke wet maatregelen covid-19).' December 1, 2020.
- Netherlands (2020) 'Law No. 44337/2020, Memorie van Toelichting (MvT). Kamerstukken II 2019/20, 35526, nr. 3.' July 28, 2020.
- Netherlands (2020) 'Law No. 62031/2020. Regeling van de Ministers van Volksgezondheid, Welzijn en Sport, van Justitie en Veiligheid en van Binnenlandse Zaken en Koninkrijksrelaties van 19 november 2020, kenmerk 1784401-214492-WJZ, houdende tijdelijke bepalingen voor het Europese deel van Nederland in verband met maatregelen ter bestrijding van de epidemie van covid-19 (Tijdelijke regeling maatregelen covid-19).' November 30, 2020.
- Netherlands (2021) 'Law No. 93/2021. Besluit van 18 februari 2021, houdende de tweede verlenging van de geldingsduur van de Tijdelijke wet maatregelen covid-19.' February 18, 2021.
- Netherlands (2021) 'Law No. 232/2021. Besluit van 17 mei 2021, houdende verlenging van de geldingsduur van de Tijdelijke wet maatregelen covid-19.' May 17, 2021.
- Netherlands (2021) 'Law No. 393/2021. Besluit van 16 augustus 2021, houdende de derde verlenging van de geldingsduur van de Tijdelijke wet maatregelen covid-19.' August 16, 2021.
- Netherlands (2021) 'Law No. 549/2021. Besluit van 22 november 2021, houdende de vierde verlenging van de geldingsduur van de Tijdelijke wet maatregelen covid-19.' November 22, 2021.
- Netherlands (2021) 'Law No. 3656/2021. Convenant versterking testketen Corona.' January 28, 2021.
- Netherlands (2022) 'Law No. 76/2022. Besluit van 21 februari 2021, houdende de vijfde verlenging van de geldingsduur van de Tijdelijke wet maatregelen covid-19.' Februari 21, 2021.
- Netherlands (2024) 'Law No. 5/2024. Wet van 24 januari 2024 tot wijziging van de Wet publieke gezondheid in verband met het afschalen van de A-status van covid-19.' January 24, 2024.

⁴⁶ The monthly updates are Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2021a-k, 2022a-g, 2023a-c).

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Secondary sources

- Ministry of Justice and Safety (2020) Inzet nationale crisisstructuur COVID-19. Letter to the chair of parliament, March 13 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020a) 'Aanwijzing evenementen afgelasten.' March 13, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020b) 'Aanvullende aanwijzing COVID-19.' March 15, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020c) 'Tweede aanvulling op aanwijzing COVID-19.' March 15, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020d) 'Aanwijzing verpleeghuizen en kleinschalige woonvormen.' March 20, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020e) 'Extra uitzondering aanwijzing COVID-19 onderwijsinstellingen.' March 23, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020f) 'Aanvulling aanwijzing COVID-19.' March 24, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020g) 'Tweede aanvulling op aanwijzing COVID-19.' March 31, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020i) 'Aanvullende aanwijzing COVID-19 maatregelen inkomende passagiers uit hoog-risicolanden.' April 16, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020j) 'Verlenging maatregelen COVID-19.' April 24, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020k) 'Aanwijzing d.d. 24 april 2020.' May 8, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020l) 'Aanwijzing maatregelen COVID-19 vanaf 1 juni.' May 26, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020m) 'Aanwijzing maatregelen COVID-19 vanaf 15 juni.' June 11, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020n) 'Aanpassing aanwijzing COVID-19.' June 12, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020o) 'Aanvullende aanwijzing Covid-19 en luchthavens.' June 19, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020p) 'Aanwijzing maatregelen covid-19 vanaf 1 juli.' Juni 26, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020q) 'Aanwijzing luchtvaartmaatregelen.' Juni 30, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020r) 'Aanwijzing per 15 juli.' Juli 10, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020s) 'Aanvullende aanwijzing 7 augustus 2020.' Augustus 7, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020t) 'Aanwijzing introductieweken studenten.' Augustus 20, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020u) 'Aanwijzing per 1 september.' September 1, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020v) 'Aanvulling aanwijzing gebruik niet-medische mondkapjes op luchthavens.' September 1, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020w) 'Aanvulling aanwijzing leerling- en doelgroepenvervoer.' September 11, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020x) 'Aanwijzing miv 20 september.' September 18, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020y) 'Aanwijzing miv 27 september.' September 25, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020z) 'Aanwijzing miv 29 september.' September 28, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020aa) 'Aanwijzing miv 14 oktober.' Oktober 14, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020ab) 'Aanwijzing miv 4 november.' November 4, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020ac) 'Aanwijzing miv 18 november.' November 18, 2020.

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- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2020ad) 'Brief VWS aan GGD inzake covid-19 vaccinatie.' December 16, 2020.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2021a) 'Stand van zakenbrief Covid-19.' January 21, 2021.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2021b) 'Stand van zakenbrief Covid-19.' February 2, 2021.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2021c) 'Stand van zakenbrief Covid-19.' March 23, 2021.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2021d) 'Stand van zakenbrief Covid-19.' April 13, 2021.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2021e) 'Stand van zakenbrief Covid-19.' May 11, 2021.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2021f) 'Stand van zakenbrief Covid-19.' June 18, 2021.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2021g) 'Stand van zakenbrief Covid-19.' July 6, 2021.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2021h) 'Stand van zakenbrief Covid-19.' August 13, 2021.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2021i) 'Stand van zakenbrief Covid-19.' September 14, 2021.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2021j) 'Stand van zakenbrief Covid-19.' November 2, 2021.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2021k) 'Stand van zakenbrief Covid-19.' December 14, 2021.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2022a) 'Stand van zakenbrief Covid-19.' January 14, 2022.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2022b) 'Stand van zakenbrief Covid-19.' February 15, 2022.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2022c) 'Verzamelbrief COVID-19.' March 22, 2022.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2022d) 'Verzamelbrief COVID-19.' May 30, 2022.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2022e) 'Verzamelbrief COVID-19.' July 4, 2022.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2022f) 'Verzamelbrief COVID-19.' November 22, 2022.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2022f) 'Lange termijn aanpak COVID-19.' September 16, 2022.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2022g) 'Verzamelbrief COVID-19.' November 22, 2022.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2023a) 'Besluiten resterende adviezen COVID-19.' March 10, 2023.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2023b) 'Diverse onderwerpen met betrekking tot het COVID-19 virus.' April 25, 2023.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2023c) 'Diverse onderwerpen met betrekking tot het COVID-19 virus.' December 18, 2023.
- Minister voor Medische Zorg en Sport (2023d) 'Afschalen A-status COVID-19.' June 16, 2023.
- Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu (2020) *Landelijke advisering bij infectieziektedreigingen en -crises*. Bilthoven: Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu.
- Veiligheidsberaad (2017) Statuut Veiligheidsberaad. 15 December 2017.
- Veiligheidsberaad (2020a) Modelnoodverordening COVID-19 bij aanwijzing van 15 maart 2020.
- Veiligheidsberaad (2020b) Modelnoodverordening COVID-19 bij aanwijzing van 24 april 2020.
- Veiligheidsberaad (2020c) Modelnoodverordening COVID-19 bij aanwijzing van 8 mei 2020.
- Veiligheidsberaad (2020d) Modelnoodverordening COVID-19 bij aanwijzing van 26 mei 2020.
- Veiligheidsberaad (2020e) Modelnoodverordening COVID-19 bij aanwijzing van 15 juli 2020.
- Veiligheidsberaad (2020f) Modelnoodverordening COVID-19 bij aanwijzing van 10 augustus 2020.
- Veiligheidsberaad (2020g) Modelnoodverordening COVID-19 bij aanwijzing van 20 september 2020.
- Veiligheidsberaad (2020h) Modelnoodverordening COVID-19 bij aanwijzing van 14 oktober 2020.
- Veiligheidsberaad (2020i) Modelnoodverordening COVID-19 bij aanwijzing van 6 november 2020.
- Veiligheidsberaad (2020j) Modelnoodverordening COVID-19 bij aanwijzing van 18 november 2020.
- Veiligheidsberaad (2020k) *Beleidskader Tijdelijke wet maatregelen COVID-19 voorzitters veiligheidsregio*. Available at: <https://www.veiligheidsberaad.nl/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/20201119-Beleidskader-Tijdelijke-wet-maatregelen-COVID-19-voorzitters-veiligheidsregio.pdf>
- Vereniging voor Nederlandse Gemeenten (VNG) (2020) *Voorbeeld-beleidskader Twm voor burgemeesters*. Available at: <https://vng.nl/sites/default/files/2020-11/voorbeeld-beleidskader-twm-voor-burgemeesters.pdf>

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Table 1. Self-rule during the Covid-19 crisis in the Netherlands.

Subnational tier		Date of a policy change				CC policies														HS policies			Total scores													
Name	Actor	A	d	m	year	5		6		7		8		10		11		12		14		16		17		18		24		25		26		CC	HS	TOT
Gemeenten	Mayor	1	1	1	2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0,000	0,000	0,000
Gemeenten	Mayor	1	13	3	2020	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0,102	0,000	0,070
Gemeenten	Mayor	1	1	7	2020	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0,114	0,000	0,078	
Gemeenten	Mayor	1	1	12	2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0,034	0,000	0,023		
Gemeenten	Mayor	1	21	1	2021	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0,034	0,075	0,047	
Gemeenten	Mayor	1	20	5	2022	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0,000	0,075	0,023	
Gemeenten	Mayor	1	1	1	2023	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0,000	0,000	0,000		
Provincies		1	1	1	2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0,000	0,000	0,000		
Provincies		1	1	1	2023	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0,000	0,000	0,000		

Notes:

CC = Containment and closure policies.

HS = Health system policies.

See §4 (page 11) for policy labels and categorization of 32 policies into CC or HS policies.

Scores for policy numbers 1-4, 9, 13, 15, 19-23, 27-32 are 0 for both *Gemeenten* and *Provincies* for the whole time period.

Shared rule scores are 0 for *Gemeenten* for the whole time period.

Shared rule (DEPTH-SH) scores for *Provincies* (ACTOR-SH= 2):

0 between 1 January 2020 and 30 March 2020.

3 between 31 March 2020 and 20 May 2022.

0 between 21 May 2022 and 31 December 2022.

Figure 1. Self-rule during the Covid-19 crisis in the Netherlands.

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